

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

Co-funded by the
European Union

D6.1 Analysis of AS-IS situation of River Pilots.

Innovation implementation & assessment plans including
infrastructure corridor analysis and simulation-based
analysis of predicted flows

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission System
AGN	Agreement on Main Inland Waterways of International importance
Aipo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
CEP	Courier Express Parcel
EPRS	Directorate-General for European Parliamentary Research Service
EU	European Union
FOS	Fiber Optic Sensors
GA	Grant Agreement

IBS	Intelligent Buoys System
IV	Infrastrutture Venete S.r. l
IWT	Inland waterway transport
KET	Key enabling technologies
KPI	Key performance indicator
LNG	Liquid Natural Gas
ML	Machine Learning
NST	Standard goods classification for transport statistics
SB	Smart Buoys
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data acquisition
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
STOA	Scientific Foresight Unit
tkm	Tonne-kilometres
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
VCC	Value Creation Circle
VNF	Voies navigables de France

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1. Executive Summary

The "Analysis of AS-IS Situation of River Pilots: Innovation implementation & assessment plans Including infrastructure corridor analysis and simulation-based analysis of predicted flows" report offers a comprehensive examination of the Inland Water Transportation (IWT) industry's present condition, while outlining strategies for innovation implementation and assessment. The report focuses on the detailed analysis of the existing IWT landscape, identification of challenges, innovation plans, and the anticipated impacts of these innovations at both regional and EU levels.

The report initiates with an in-depth analysis of the current situation, encompassing key aspects such as the state of the IWT industry in various regions, infrastructure availability along the corridor's main river routes, IWT planning and organization processes, and the management of the crucial infrastructure components. The comprehensive analysis serves as the foundation for subsequent tasks, including the identification of primary needs and problems affecting IWT, understanding the factors influencing infrastructure resilience, and examining potential disruptions within the IWT sector.

The determination of baseline and test definition further refines the investigation. The report outlines the meticulous planning process, which involves designing and executing pilot studies in three different countries – Italy, France, and Poland. Each pilot study is extensively detailed, providing insight into the specific goals, case specifications, involved actors, technologies, and infrastructure. The report also presents a holistic view of expected pilot outcomes and assessment methodologies, ensuring the comprehensive evaluation of the proposed innovations.

Central to the report is the innovation plan, which outlines a strategic approach for addressing the identified challenges through the integration of new technologies and concepts. This plan emphasizes a forward-thinking approach to problem-solving and optimization, fostering the development of innovative solutions that can reshape the IWT landscape.

The report concludes by discussing the expected impact of the adopted innovations at both regional and EU levels. This section underscores the projected outcomes of the implemented innovations, highlighting how they align with the broader goals of the IWT industry and contribute to the advancement of sustainable and efficient transportation networks.

In summary, the "Analysis of AS-IS Situation of River Pilots: Innovation implementation & assessment plans Including infrastructure corridor analysis and simulation-based analysis of predicted flows" report provides a comprehensive roadmap for enhancing the IWT industry's efficiency, resilience, and sustainability. By meticulously analyzing the current state, identifying challenges, and proposing innovative solutions, the report contributes to the advancement of the European transportation sector. This comprehensive approach ensures that the industry remains at the forefront of technological and operational advancements, paving the way for a more resilient and adaptable future.

1.1. Introduction

Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) has long been recognized as a vital component of regional and intercontinental logistics networks, offering a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable mode of freight transportation. As the world navigates through a dynamic era of technological advancements and changing economic landscapes, it becomes imperative to conduct a thorough assessment of the current state of IWT, scrutinizing its infrastructural aspects, operational efficiency, and the challenges it faces. This report serves as a comprehensive analysis, aimed at dissecting the intricate web of factors influencing IWT, with a particular focus on the corridor's infrastructure, identifying key needs and issues, and delineating the path towards a resilient and innovative future. In the pursuit of a comprehensive overview, this report delves into the present condition of IWT in different regions, analyzes the infrastructure supporting this mode of transport, and dissects the planning and management processes that underpin its operations. By identifying the main needs and challenges, as well as assessing the factors affecting infrastructure resilience and the disruptions faced, this report establishes a robust baseline. Furthermore, it outlines pilot initiatives from various regions in Italy, France and Poland, each aiming to address specific issues, while also spotlighting an innovation plan poised to shape the trajectory of IWT. Lastly, by evaluating the expected impact of these innovations, both at regional and EU levels, this report lays the foundation for a transformative journey in the realm of inland waterway transport.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D6.1 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL Component Title	GA CRISTAL Outline	GA Component	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE				
<i>D6.1 Analysis of AS-IS situation of River Pilots. Innovation implementation & assessment plans including infrastructure corridor analysis and simulation-based analysis of predicted flows.</i>	<i>Analysis of AS-IS situation of River Pilots.</i>		<i>Chapter 2 In-depth analysis of the current situation & Chapter 6 Determination of baseline and test definition</i>	<i>An in-depth analysis of the current situation, encompassing key aspects such as the state of the IWT industry in various regions, infrastructure availability along the corridor's main river routes, IWT planning and organization processes, and the management of the crucial infrastructure components.</i> <i>The determination of baseline and test definition further refines the investigation. The report</i>

			<p><i>outlines the meticulous planning process, which involves designing and executing pilot studies in three different countries – Italy, France, and Poland</i></p>
	<p><i>Innovation implementation & assessment plans including infrastructure corridor analysis and simulation-based analysis of predicted flows.</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 7. Innovation plan & Chapter 8. Expected impact of adopted innovations at the regional and EU level & Sub-chapter 2.2. Infrastructure for the corridor (Main river routes and alternative transport modes)</i></p>	<p><i>Innovation plan outlines a strategic approach for addressing the identified challenges through the integration of new technologies and concepts. This plan emphasizes a forward-thinking approach to problem-solving and optimization, fostering the development of innovative solutions that can reshape the IWT landscape.</i></p> <p><i>The expected impact of the adopted innovations at both regional and EU levels. This section underscores the projected outcomes of the implemented innovations, highlighting how they align with the broader goals of the IWT industry and contribute to the advancement of sustainable and efficient transportation networks.</i></p>
TASKS			
<p>Task 6.1 LL AS-IS analysis and detailed specification plan</p>	<p><i>Provide an in-depth analysis of the current situation, including infrastructure analysis for the corridor</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 2. In-depth analysis of the current situation</i></p> <p><i>2.1. Current situation of the IWT industry in each region</i></p>	<p><i>The initial phase of the study involved an in-depth analysis of the corridor under examination. This analysis encompassed a holistic evaluation of the existing infrastructure, including the assessment of waterway conditions, examination of ports and</i></p>

		<p><i>2.2. Infrastructure for the corridor (Main river routes and alternative transport modes)</i></p>	<p><i>terminals, and an evaluation of intermodal connections. By scrutinizing these aspects, we aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the corridor's current state and its potential for accommodating and optimizing IWT operations.</i></p>
	<p><i>(i) the identification of main needs and problems affecting use of IWT that will be addressed in the RPs;</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 3. Identification of main needs and problems affecting IWT</i></p>	<p><i>Building upon the insights gained from the infrastructure analysis, our study identified and prioritized the main needs and problems that hinder the effective use of Inland Waterway Transport within the corridor. These challenges encompassed a wide range of factors, such as outdated infrastructure, inadequate navigational conditions, inefficient intermodal interfaces, and regulatory barriers. The identification of these issues forms the basis for developing targeted solutions and interventions</i></p>
	<p><i>(ii) determine the baseline as described above and provide the definition of tests based on new technologies and concepts proposed in order to overcome the selected problems; (iii) the final selection of specific supply chains or transport flows to perform the tests, affecting specific shippers, corridors, logistics nodes and transport and logistic stakeholders.</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 6. Determination of baseline and test definition</i></p>	<p><i>To establish a baseline for performance assessment and measure the impact of potential improvements, we defined the existing state of the corridor in terms of various performance indicators. This baseline assessment involved the collection and analysis of relevant data to benchmark the current performance levels and identify areas for improvement. Drawing from</i></p>

		<p><i>this baseline, we formulated a comprehensive set of tests and KPIs that leverage new technologies and concepts to overcome the challenges identified earlier. These tests were designed to evaluate the efficacy of innovative solutions in enhancing the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of IWT operations within the corridor. By targeting specific supply chains, we aimed to assess the real-world applicability and impact of the proposed solutions on the corridor's transportation network.</i></p>
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The deliverable provides a comprehensive analysis of the inland water transportation (IWT) industry (**Chapter 2.**), focusing on its current state (**Subchapter 2.1.**), challenges, and potential for innovation. It examines the infrastructure (**Subchapter 2.2.**), planning, and organization processes within different regions (**Subchapter 2.3.**). The report identifies key needs and problems affecting IWT (**Chapter 3.**), explores factors influencing infrastructure resilience (**Chapter 4.**), and discusses disruptions faced by the industry (**Chapter 5.**). The deliverable also outlines a baseline and test definition approach, including detailed pilot cases from Italy, France, and Poland (**Chapter 6.**). It concludes by presenting an innovation plan (**Chapter 7.**), highlighting the anticipated impact of adopted innovations at both regional and EU levels (**Chapter 8.**). The report culminates in insightful conclusions drawn from the analysis, supported by references for further exploration (**Chapter 9. and 10. respectively**).

2. In-depth analysis of the current situation

The initial phase of the study involved an in-depth analysis of the corridor under examination. This analysis encompassed a holistic evaluation of the existing infrastructure, including the assessment of waterway conditions, examination of ports and terminals, and an evaluation of intermodal connections in pilot regions – Poland, France and Italy. By scrutinizing these aspects, we aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the corridor's current state and its potential for accommodating and optimizing IWT operations.

2.1. Current situation of the IWT industry in each region

Poland

Poland's inland waterway network is 3767km, 94% of which are navigable, but only 2329km are in operation. The potential of Poland's main inland waterways cannot compare with that of the waterways of Germany, the Netherlands, or Belgium, even though the length of our waterway network is one of the longest in Europe, with only the Netherlands, France, Finland and Germany having a longer waterway network. Poland's main rivers are the Vistula and Oder, included in the AGN international waterway network system, covering the area of inland waterways from the Atlantic to the Urals. Poland's main rivers follow a meridional pattern and drain into the Baltic Sea.

The problem of Polish waterways is low performance. Only 5.9% of Poland's waterways achieve Class IV or V navigability, allowing free navigation at the international level, and this is mainly the section of the Lower Oder River near Szczecin, also included as the only one in the international RIS network. The Oder and Vistula, Poland's main rivers, are part of the AGN international waterway network, yet the Vistula along its entire length and the Oder along half of its length does not exceed Class III navigability.

Figure 1 Polish inland waterway main corridors

Source: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-61965-7_18

However, there are many arguments in favor of the development of waterways in Poland - the primary waterways (Oder, Vistula) connect the rapidly developing seaports with the hinterland, other modes of transport cannot meet the growing inland shipping needs, Polish inland waterways are connected to the network of European waterways, which creates conditions for the development of international shipping. The significant demand for water from other economic areas, the flood risk and energy potential of the lower Vistula River, and the attractive riverside areas as tourist assets are arguments for multifunctional waterway management, which will not only improve shipping conditions, but could prove very profitable for the economy. The low level of funding for the development and maintenance of inland waterways compared to other modes of transport has not only prevented waterways from achieving the required technical class, but has also caused their serious deterioration. The requirements for international waterways in Poland, i.e. waterways of class IV and higher, met only 5.9% of waterways in 2017, i.e. 214 km out of 3654 km of navigable inland waterways. This share in Poland has remained at the same level since 2007. The problem of minor use for transportation even affects the Oder River, considered the best waterway in Poland. The technical parameters of this waterway on 50.7% of its length do not even meet the requirements for Class III. Out of a total of 47 on this waterway, there are only 2 navigable weirs that meet the technical conditions for at least Class IV. Limited clearances under bridges are another source of serious problems. As many as 60 bridges on the Oder waterway do not meet the requirements for Class IV, including 39 road bridges and 18 rail bridges. In 2017, the volume of freight transport on the Oder Waterway (Oder and Gliwice Canal) amounted to 2.1 million tons. Navigational difficulties are even greater on the Vistula River. As much as 80% of the waterway's length has only Class I and II parameters, which is too low for modern navigation requirements to ensure profitable cargo shipping. The upper Vistula is as unimportant for transportation as the lower Vistula. Inland freight transport on the upper Vistula is limited to short-distance shipping. Currently, permanent transport cannot be carried out on the

middle Vistula (from the mouth of the Sanna River to the mouth of the Narew River). Since this section remains unmaintained and grows wild, there is also no tourist or recreational navigation in this section.

The weak technical parameters of Poland's waterways, their diversity and their increasingly deteriorating condition make it difficult to organize long-distance transportation. This, in turn, results in a spatial contraction of services on the inland waterway market. Local transportation takes place primarily on the lower and upper Vistula. Process transport (primarily for aggregate extracted from the riverbed) takes place on this section of the Vistula. In 2017, the average distance of such transport on the lower Vistula was 2.3 km and 8 km on the upper Vistula.

Continued neglect of inland waterway investment projects has made the outlook for domestic inland waterway transportation overly optimistic. The volume of freight transportation currently on Polish waterways accounts for only 0.1% of land transportation in Poland. The main commodities that are transported by inland waterways are metal ores, coal and agricultural products. Given the observed trends, it can be expected that the importance of the transport function of European inland waterways will not decrease in the long term, but the decline in the use of inland waterways in transport in Poland is inconsistent with the adopted EU priorities for sustainable transport development. The limited ability to perform the transport function of inland waterways is a consequence of neglecting the maintenance of multifunctional inland waterways, and the development of Polish inland waterway transport is a prerequisite for the sustainable growth rate of seaports and their position in Europe. The need to increase the importance of waterways for transportation stems from Poland's declaration on the adaptation of inland waterways of international importance to the requirements of the AGN Agreement, ratified on March 6, 2017.

Italy

In Italy, freight and passenger transportation develops almost entirely along the Po River and its adjacent canals. The territory is characterized by a river system linking the Po River and artificial waterways or canals (the Padano-Veneto waterway system), used to transport goods and passengers. The Po River, located in northern Italy and flowing into the Adriatic Sea, is the country's longest - 652km and largest river, with a basin area of 74tys km².

Figure 2 Inland waterway system of river Po
 Source: uence.org

Within the Po River, an important artificial waterway in Italy is the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbionco Canal, which connects Mantua to the Adriatic Sea as an alternative to the Po River. Another strategic part of the system is the section connecting Milan, the country's productive economic center, with Cremona. The waterway system of northern Italy and the northern Adriatic provides an opportunity to link the numerous industrial activities of the Po Valley and the Adriatic Sea through an east-west connection.

Figure 3 River Po inland waterway system Source: Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po – AIPo
 Source: <https://www.actu-transport-logistique.fr/npi-magazine/thematiques/acteurs/la-ccnr-a-passe-au-crible-le-transport-fluvial-en-italie-778173.php>

Considering the navigability of the Po River, it is necessary to examine five sections that completely cover the navigability of the river from west to east. The figure illustrates the river's navigability levels from 2013 to 2021. The section from Piacenza to Isola Serafini is the westernmost section of the river. The easternmost extends from Pontelagoscuero to the Volta Grimana lock near the Adriatic Sea. The two sections that connect Cremona to Mantua (Cremona - Estuarium Mincio) have shown the most favorable navigational conditions in recent years, with a two-meter draft guaranteed for an average of 270.0 days in 2020 and 137.5 days in 2021. Conversely, the sections between Mantua and Ferrara (Estuarium Mincio - Pontelagoscuero) and between Piacenza and Isola Serafini presented critical water level conditions compared to the average for the entire river.

Figure 4 Number of days with available draught levels higher or equal to 2 meters on the River Po
Source: https://inland-navigation-market.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/Rapport-semestriel-Q1-2023_EN_BD.pdf

In the past few years, the volume of freight transport in the Padano - Veneto waterway system has shown a downward trend. In 2019, the volume of freight transported decreased by 19.06%, moving from 355,222 tons registered in 2018 to 287,517 tons. The declining trend stopped in 2020, during the Covid-19 pandemic. Cross-border road transportation was significantly reduced due to lockdowns, resulting in a sudden need to increase inland transportation. The strong demand that followed lifted volumes to 858,884 tons in 2020. This growth was confirmed in 2021, when 980,000 tons of cargo were transported, and occurred despite rather difficult hydrological conditions on the Po River. In terms of million ton-miles, Italy's inland waterway freight volume in 2020 increased significantly by 69.1 million ton-miles (+125.87 percent) from 2019.

Figure 5 Freight transported by IWW in Italy 2007-2020

Source: <https://www.statista.com/>

Other drivers of inland transportation in Italy are coming from public initiatives. In 2019, the Italian government issued a decree supporting inland waterway freight transport, aiming to improve modal share in the future. Within the Padano-Veneto waterway system, the port of Mantua and its adjacent industrial wharves are two key points for inland waterway freight transport in Italy. The city is strategically positioned to connect its port to the Adriatic Sea via the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco Canal and the Po River. In addition, the location of chemical plants near the port favors the economic activity of the inland waterway sector in the area. Another important cargo segment is the metallurgical industry. Oversize cargo has always been a large volume for the PadanoVeneto water transport sector.

Passenger transport plays an important role in local public transportation and tourism and is highly developed on the lakes in northern Italy and the Venetian Lagoon. However, the passenger sector was severely affected by the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020, but nevertheless, data for 2021 suggest a return to pre-pandemic levels.

France

River transportation in France is a means of transporting goods and passengers using the network of canals and navigable rivers located within the country. With 6.7 billion ton-miles in 2018, or about 1.82% of all national land traffic, it occupies a secondary position compared to road and rail transport. Traffic is divided into five main river basins (Seine , Rhine , North , Moselle and Rhône-Saône), although the entire length of all river routes in France account for 8500 km of navigable waterways, the first in Europe in terms of length. However, only 4,100 kilometers are dedicated to freight traffic, and 2,000 kilometers are sized for modern commercial operations.

Figure 6 Inland waterway network in France

Source: https://www.ccr-zkr.org/files/documents/om/om22_II_en.pdf

The main goods transported are construction materials (32.2% of the total in million t-km), agri-food products (30.4%), energy products (15.1%), containers , heavy packaging and vehicles (9.8%), chemicals (6.4%) and steel products (6.1%). More than 50% of this traffic (3.9 million t-km) is concentrated in the Seine basin, which connects two important ports, Rouen and Le Havre, to a major consumption area, Île-de-France and a leading grain-producing region. The role of inland shipping is much more limited than in neighboring countries with similar river networks, such as Germany (64 million t-km), Belgium (8.75 million t-km) and the Netherlands Low (45 million t-km) . Several reasons can be cited, notably the lack of concentration of people outside of Ile-de-France, the small volumes of goods traditionally handled by this mode of transport related in particular to the rapid decline in coal production after World War II , the decline of the steel industry and the importance of nuclear power in energy production. River traffic is focused on heavy products - construction materials, grain, coal, oil products, ores, vehicles.

Figure 7 Inland waterway freight transport in France [tonno kilometers, million]

Source: https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?&datasetcode=ITF_GOODS_TRANSPORT#

With 6,700 km of canals and developed rivers, the VNF manages and operates the largest waterway network in Europe. Most commercial traffic is carried on the Seine and two of its tributaries, the Oise and Marne. In this system, broad gauge routes take the lion's share. They allow barge convoys of 185 meters, consisting of a pusher and barges capable of transporting up to 5,000 tons, to pass. This is enough to remove 200 trucks from the roads - in fact, river transport emits four times less CO₂ per volume carried than road transport.

The Moselle, is a 392-kilometer-long waterway with 28 water stages, and is a left tributary of the Rhine. It is an international waterway connecting the economically developed regions of Lorraine, Luxembourg, Saarland and Trier Land in Germany with the North Sea ports of the Netherlands and Belgium. As a result of work carried out since 1958 to channelize individual sections, and dredge the waterway to 3m, it is accessible to 6,000-ton push sets and 3,000-ton motor barges. A gradual decline in cargo was observed on the Moselle between 2005 and 2018, from 14 million tons to 9 million tons in 2018. The intensity of ship traffic also decreased by an exemplary 8,000 locks at the Koblenz Lock between 2008 and 2018. The reduced shipping traffic on the Moselle is due not only to low water levels, but also to the reduced capacity of the locks, which in many cases prevent the use of modern motor barges, which are becoming increasingly popular in Western Europe. Fluctuations in water flow have been observed on the Moselle in recent years. Problems with low water levels on the routes and nets are particularly prevalent for smaller vessels, affecting the broad gauge network. Future consequences for the tourism sector are also expected. Real-time monitoring of infrastructure and water depths is therefore crucial. Currently, some amount of data is already being captured, as many sensors are installed on the infrastructure; the VNF is working on the issue of connected objects (IoT).

2.2. Infrastructure for the corridor (Main river routes and alternative transport modes)

Poland

Poland has been rapidly expanding its road, rail, air and sea infrastructure. Due to its strategic location at the intersection of the main transport routes on both the north-south and the east-west lines, Poland places a lot of emphasis on maintaining a strong position on the logistics map of Europe. Major projects such as the “Solidarity” Transport Hub, Polish involvement in the Belt and Road initiative, and the North-south “via Carpatia” route testify to Poland’s position as a regional leader.

Transit traffic between Western and Southern Europe and the countries of the eastern part of the continent (including i.e. Estonia, Belarus, Lithuania, Latvia, Russia, Ukraine and Kazakhstan) and China runs through Poland. Poland is crossed by routes of international importance, including international road corridors of TEN-T network (Corridor Baltic-Adriatic, North Sea- Baltic Sea).

Figure 8 Motorways and expressways in Poland

Source: https://www.paih.gov.pl/Strategic_location_in_the_heart_of_Europe

In Polish transport network also is an important railway network, with international railways included in International Rail Freight Corridors (5,7,11), both passenger and freight lines. In the multimodal transport chain, there are 43 intermodal terminals in Poland, mostly situated alongside main rail corridors and near main routes.

Figure 9 Railfreight corridors in Poland

Source: Jakubowski, T. Komornicki, K. Kowalczyk " Poland as a hub of the Silk Road Economic Belt: is the narrative of opportunity supported by developments on the ground

Inland waterway infrastructure in Poland is underdeveloped. Along Poland's largest rivers Oder and Vistula, there are currently no multimodal transshipment terminals in operation. Along the Oder River, it is possible to use transshipment ports in Police, Szczecin, Wrocław and Gliwice for transshipment between transport modes. The most advanced in terms of multimodality is the trimodal port in Gliwice, where river-to-rail transshipment of containerized cargo is possible, although underutilized.

Figure 10 Polish inland waterway network with ports

Source: uence.org

The network of transport infrastructure in Poland partly coincides with the course of the main river corridors. A well-developed network of expressways and highways allows wheeled transport to reach almost any transshipment point from inland transportation. Railroad lines run in directions similar to the course of the rivers. Particularly in the Lower and Middle Oder sections, the CE-59 railroad runs along the river and could ensure the substitutability of river transportation. In the area of the Vistula River, it is possible to partially support it with rail transportation via the CE-65 railroad to Bydgoszcz, or the E-65 to Warsaw. Work is also underway to develop a trimodal transshipment terminal in Solec Kujawski to enable river-rail transshipment in the central Vistula area. To date, however, the lack of publicly accessible transshipment terminals equipped with transshipment facilities poses a major challenge to the organization of multimodal transshipment chains using inland waterway transport.

Italy

Most goods (more than 60%) in Italy are transported by truck, and within Italy, the figure is as high as 80%. In particular, road transport dominates freight traffic with the two most important trading partners, Germany and France. Compared to the pre-Corona year 2019, road freight journeys increased by 2.5% in 2021 – especially journeys over the Alpine passes recorded large increases. By 2030, however, freight traffic is expected to shift increasingly to rail, so that 25-30% of freight should then be transported by rail, and by 2050 the figure should be as high as 50%. Italy is in a strategic position because four of the nine corridors of the TEN-T core network, which are essential for increasing connectivity between European markets, pass through Italy:

- Baltic-Adriatic,

- Scandinavia-Mediterranean,
- Rhine-Alps
- Mediterranean.

To reflect increasing transport flows and the evolution of the TEN-T, EU Regulation 2021/1153 provides for adjustments to the core network corridors and related sections identified in advance. These adjustments concern: the Mediterranean CNC with sections Ventimiglia - Genoa and La Spezia - Novara, and the Baltic - Adriatic CNC with an extension to the port of Ancona.

Italy's transportation infrastructure is largely based on road transportation. In terms of rail network length, Italy ranks 54th in the world with 0.29 meters per capita. The total length of the rail network is 16,779 kilometers. Freight traffic on the tracks recently reached 24.26 billion tons and kilometers traveled. Passenger traffic reached 27.69 billion passenger-kilometer in 2021.

	total
Roadways	487,700 km
Railroads	16,800 km
Waterways	2,400 km
Commercial harbors	1,296
Airports	43

Figure 11 Transport infrastructure in Italy
Source: WorldData.info

There are 50 intermodal terminals within reach of the railroads, allowing transshipment between rail and road.

Figure 12 Railway Ten-T network in Italy with rail road terminals
Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/transport/infrastructure/tentec/tentec-portal/map/maps.html?layer=1,2,3,4,5,6,8,9&country=IT>

The main and only inland waterway in Italy runs on the Po River. There are river ports on the river that allow cargo handling, and in just one port multimodal transshipment from inland transport to rail would be possible (Port of Mantova).

Figure 13 Inland waterway and rail network in the region of Po River. Ports and multimodal terminals included.
Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/transport/infrastructure/tentec/tentec-portal/map/maps.html?layer=1,2,3,4,5,6,8,9&country=IT>

France

The transport (national and international) of goods in France is dominated by road transport, with more than 2 billion goods transported every year. Road transport of goods is above all practical. Due to the size of the country and its location in the middle of Europe, but also due to its importance as a country with large manufacturing industries, French roads continue to be among the most important for European-wide international road freight transport: 18.3 % of all tonne-kilometres performed in international road freight transport took place in France, according to latest data by Eurostat. Plans for putting trucks on trains and reviving the use of waterways could advance the development of a form of transport other than roads, but their potential remains limited.

Figure 14 Freight transport in France 2010-2021 [mln tonnes kilometers]

Source: <https://stats.oecd.org/>

France is important part of TEN-T corridors. The corridors that run through the French network are the following:

- Mediterranean Corridor, from the Spanish border at Perpignan to the Italian border via Lyon and Marseille.
- Atlantic Corridor, from the Spanish border at Hendaye to the German border at Strasbourg and a branch to Mannheim, via Bordeaux, Paris and Metz.
- North Sea-Mediterranean Corridor, from the UK border (Channel Tunnel) to Lille and the Belgian border, then from Luxembourg southbound to Marseille, via Dijon and Lyon.
- Rhine-Danube Corridor, starting in Strasbourg.

As can be seen in Figure 11, in France, road transport is the main mode of transportation. 89% of flows are transported by road (54% under French flag and 35% under foreign flag). In the long term (2000-2019), road transport increased by 16% (322 billion vs. 277 billion tkm in 2000). Water transport remained stable,

pipeline transport fell 45%, and rail transport lost 43% of its volumes. Rail freight in France accounts for a 9% share of total transport volumes. To prevent further declines in rail freight, a rescue plan signed by the state, SNCF Réseau, the 4F alliance (French rail freight of the future), and AUTF (shippers) was developed in 2021. Each year until 2024, €170 million will be allocated to support rail freight operators. In addition, investments will be made as part of the reconstruction plan (estimated at €1 billion). In July 2021, the Climate and Resilience Act, specifically Article 30ter, set ambitious targets for doubling rail freight's share of freight transport by 2030. The main problem in rail freight in France is the prioritization of passenger trains on lines where freight trains also run, so that freight trains are shunted to tracks outside cities and their average route speed is 20km/h for the whole country. There are also bottlenecks, such as the Lyon crossing, which has been waiting for a rail bypass for more than 20 years.

Figure 15 Network coverage in France

Source: Own elaboration

Multimodal infrastructure in France is well developed. There are 52 intermodal terminals in France, of which more than 10 can be classified as trimodal terminals allowing transshipment between inland waterway, rail and road transport.

2.3. IWT planning and organization process

Managing the corridor from the logistics side is a very demanding and complicated task. The subchapter "Inland Waterway Transport Planning and Organization Process" delves into the intricate mechanics of orchestrating the movement of goods and cargo through inland waterways, unveiling the integral framework that ensures the smooth navigation of these aquatic pathways. This process encompasses the strategic planning, coordination, and execution of transportation activities, all aimed at optimizing the utilization of rivers and canals for efficient and sustainable cargo delivery.

The overall logistics process

The Annex1 "CRISTAL process.pdf" depicts the flow of the logistic process of transporting goods presented in a diagram in BPMN methodology. The process illustrates the flow of cargo under the assumptions of the application of the EXW import incoterm, which involves the transportation of goods from a seaport to an inland customer.

The process was mapped on the example of polish procedures and then compared with procedures and guidelines found in Italy and France. The overall process begins when a contract is created between the manufacturer and the customer, and a transport need arises at the customer. The consignee then orders a service to transport the goods from the production site to the destination customer. The link that mediates and organises the transport is the freight forwarder.

The freight forwarder arranges the transport, and the processes of customs clearance and phytosanitary inspections, and organises the physical movement of the goods using the carriers of the particular mode of transport, with a choice of three transport paths:

- direct by road - involving the organisation of transport wholly by road (direct delivery)
- delivery with transshipment - **road - rail - road** - using road transport to bring cargo to the rail terminal, transporting cargo by rail, hauling cargo the last mile by road
- delivery with transshipment - **road - inland waterway (IWW) - road** - arrival of cargo at the inland terminal by road, transport of cargo by inland waterway, removal of cargo at the last mile by road. This process variant is detailed in the transport sub-process map in Annex2 "**CRISTAL IWW transport process.pdf**".

The overall process highlights the progression of each process option. The decision on the choice of transport branch is made at the decision gate - "Start of transport plan preparation (road, rail, IWW)". - in which, on the basis of data from the transport infrastructure and data on infrastructure availability, the shipper decides on the process flow path. The data providing the information needed to make the decision to select inland waterway transport comes from the IWW infrastructure manager, and the nature of the data and the technologies provided to collect it are presented in the Annex3 "**Infrastructure management process and roles.exl**".

During the process flow there are a number of organisational transport activities carried out by the forwarder and other process actors, including interaction with other participants and exchange of documents necessary for the organisation of transport. There is an exchange of orders, messages, documents between the process actors, leading to the finalisation of the cargo flow and the completion of the process when the cargo is delivered to the consignee and the transport order is completed.

The generic process presents a collection of process actors who perform specific activities in the process and who exchange messages, or documents, between themselves:

- producer – produces goods, sends cargo for transport
- forwarder 1'st mile – it is responsible for the organisation of the transport process
- road carrier – carries out road transport in process variants
- rail operator – operates rail transport in process variants

- facility operator – terminal of loading – divided according to the mode of transport used into rail or inland waterway loading terminal
- IWW Shipowner – inland waterway transport operator
- Facility operator – terminal of discharge – subdivided according to the mode of transport used into rail or inland waterway discharge terminals
- custom agent – carries out customs operations on cargo
- rail infrastructure manager – provides information on the availability and usability of railways
- IWW infrastructure authority – provides information on the accessibility and usability of inland waterways
- Insurance broker – insures the cargo
- Survey - inspection and sanitation services controlling the cargo
- Consignee – buys the cargo from the manufacturer, orders the transport, receives the cargo.

Inland waterway transport process

The process of organising and routing inland waterway transport in the logistics process results from a decision by the shipper to transport the cargo by inland waterway on the basis of data obtained from, among others, the infrastructure manager IWW (decision gate in the **CRISTAL Process** - "Start of transport plan preparation (road, rail, IWW)" fed with data from the infrastructure management process "**Infrastructure management process and roles.ex1**").

In the river transport sub-process, the spectrum of actors involved in organising the flow of cargo is widening:

- Forwarding company – the forwarding company which organises the transport - the forwarding department may also have a separate unit which, in the event of the need to organise a transshipment site, plays the role of organiser of temporary transshipment site.
- IWW shipowner – inland carrier organising the operation of a waterborne transport operation
- IWW infrastructure authority – infrastructure manager providing information on waterway accessibility
- Sea port – the seaport within which the Harboursmasters office - which authorises operations in the port area, the Terminal - which carries out cargo handling operations - is located
- IWW Terminal – a place on the river where unloading is possible. If no such place exists, the role of the IWW terminal is taken over by a temporary terminal organised by the Forwarding company in cooperation with entities such as the Landlord and the Operator of reloading device.
- Operator of the reloading device – entity providing trans-shipment equipment where there is no fixed river discharge terminal
- Landlord – owner of the land on which the Forwarder company is establishing a temporary reloading site.

The detailed inland transport process starts with the Forwarding company, which decides from which port and terminal and to which place and when the transport will take place, based on an order from the Consignee from the general process.

The Forwarding company orders the carriage to the IWW Shipowner and contacts the loading terminal at Sea Port, and the discharging terminal for the carriage to be advised. In the absence of an IWW destination terminal, the Forwarding company, with the involvement of the Organiser of temporary transshipment

site, organises the transshipment site on its own by agreeing the conditions of land use with the Landlord and the conditions of transshipment with the Operator of the reloading device.

The IWW Shipowner is responsible for organising the carriage, liaising with the terminals and collecting the cargo from the marine terminal, as well as obtaining any necessary approvals from the IWW infrastructure managers. The IWW Shipowner performs the physical carriage of the cargo to the terminal of destination and substitutes the cargo for unloading. At this point, with the handover of the transport documents, when the cargo is unloaded from the barge at the terminal, the detailed inland transport process is completed and the subsequent return of the cargo by road is described in the general **CRISTAL Process**.

The mapped process was considered by the partners to be generic processes, applicable to the organization of the logistics process in Europe. Depending on the degree of digitization of infrastructure and data flows, the process may be modified, as pointed out by the partners in France, where data exchange between logistics providers and transport infrastructure managers can occur automatically, without the need to initiate personal contact.

2.4. Infrastructure management process

From a manager's perspective, the process of maintaining river infrastructure involves a range of activities aimed at ensuring the continued functionality, safety, and efficiency of the infrastructure. Here is a detailed overview of the typical process:

Establishing maintenance goals and strategies:

- a. Assessment and planning: The manager conducts regular assessments of the condition and performance of the river infrastructure, including locks, channels, ports, and other components. This helps identify maintenance needs and prioritize activities.
- b. Setting maintenance goals: Based on the assessment, the manager establishes specific maintenance goals, such as maintaining navigability, reducing downtime, ensuring safety, and optimizing the lifespan of the infrastructure.
- c. Developing maintenance strategies: The manager develops strategies to address identified maintenance needs, considering factors such as available resources, budget constraints, and the urgency of repairs. This may involve implementing preventive maintenance, predictive maintenance, or corrective maintenance approaches.

Budgeting and resource allocation:

- a. Financial planning: The manager prepares a maintenance budget based on the identified needs and strategies. This involves estimating costs for materials, labor, equipment, and external services.
- b. Resource allocation: The manager allocates resources, including personnel, equipment, and materials, to ensure the timely execution of maintenance activities. This may involve coordinating with internal teams, outsourcing certain tasks, or partnering with external contractors.

Routine maintenance activities:

- a. Regular inspections: The manager schedules and conducts routine inspections of the infrastructure to identify any signs of wear, damage, or potential issues. Inspections may include visual checks, measurements, and the use of specialized tools or technologies.
- b. Preventive maintenance: Planned preventive maintenance activities are performed to proactively address potential issues and prevent equipment failures or infrastructure deterioration. This may involve tasks such as lubrication, cleaning, equipment calibration, and minor repairs.
- c. Repairs and corrective maintenance: When maintenance issues are identified, the manager organizes and coordinates repair efforts to address the problems promptly. This may involve scheduling repairs, procuring necessary materials, coordinating with maintenance teams or contractors, and ensuring compliance with safety regulations.

Emergency and unscheduled maintenance:

- a. Response to emergencies: In the event of emergencies, such as sudden equipment failures, structural damages, or extreme weather events, the manager takes immediate action to minimize disruptions and ensure safety. This may involve mobilizing emergency repair teams, coordinating with relevant authorities, and communicating with stakeholders.
- b. Unscheduled maintenance: Unscheduled maintenance tasks that arise unexpectedly, such as breakdowns or unforeseen damages, are addressed promptly to minimize disruptions and ensure the continued operation of the infrastructure. The manager adjusts schedules and resources as necessary to address these urgent maintenance needs.

Documentation and record-keeping:

- a. Maintenance records: The manager maintains comprehensive records of all maintenance activities, including inspections, repairs, replacements, and equipment servicing. This documentation helps track maintenance history, identify recurring issues, and plan future maintenance activities.
- b. Data analysis: The manager analyzes maintenance data, including performance metrics, maintenance records, and equipment reliability, to identify trends, optimize maintenance strategies, and make data-driven decisions for resource allocation and budgeting.

Continuous improvement and optimization:

- a. Performance evaluation: The manager regularly evaluates the effectiveness of the maintenance activities by comparing actual performance against maintenance goals and key performance indicators (KPIs). This includes analyzing data, seeking feedback from stakeholders, and conducting post-maintenance evaluations.
- b. Process optimization: Based on performance evaluations and feedback, the manager identifies areas for improvement and implements changes to optimize maintenance processes. This may involve revising

maintenance strategies, upgrading equipment, implementing new technologies, or improving training and skills development for maintenance personnel.

In the course of the work on infrastructure management, studies have been conducted on the impact of the relationship between the actions taken by infrastructure managers and the organization of the transportation process. There is a close relationship between the logistics process and infrastructure management, especially in the planning phase. As can be seen in the diagram of the logistics process, in the decision gate, in the process of organizing transportation, when deciding on the choice of transport route, it is important to obtain information about the availability of river infrastructure (as well as road and rail infrastructure when choosing between different modes of transport. This information needed to trigger the decision-making process comes largely from infrastructure managers, is made available by these managers in a publicly available information system used by the other actors in the transport process - e.g. Logistics provider. In order to examine more broadly the type of information produced by the infrastructure manager, and to trace the process of acquiring this information and managing the infrastructure collecting/sharing this information, a study was conducted in which we examined:

- Actor – river infrastructure manager
- Role – what role it plays
- What information (parameter) it provides – what information this role provides
- On what basis – on what basis it provides this information
- Source of information – where he gets this information from
- What devices it currently uses – what equipment it currently uses to obtain this information
- What infrastructure can be used with the technologies developed at CRISTAL? – what infrastructure/equipment produced by the CRISTAL project could provide this information
- From whom the information comes – from whom this information comes (currently)
- How it receives information – how it receives this information
- www if sourcing from a website - enter address here
- To whom – to whom it communicates, makes information available
- Objective – for what purpose it collects and makes this information available
- How it delivers how it delivers them to the recipients
- www – if through a website, indicate the address
- With what frequency does it provide data – with what frequency it collects/shares data
- Who maintains/monitors the device on the infrastructure – who is responsible for the maintenance of the infrastructure, equipment that is used to collect measurements/information
- For which purposes this information is used (e.g. T - for the transport process , I - maintenance of the infrastructure) – what is the purpose of collecting, transmitting this information - for the purpose of maintaining the infrastructure (I), for the purpose of carrying out transport on the river (T)
- When (at what point in the transport process) – at what point in the transport process this information is used.

A number of tasks performed by infrastructure operators were identified, which in many cases were consistent for processes in all three countries. Some of the tasks were country-specific.

Table 2 Tasks performed by infrastructure operators

Category	Role	Actor		
		WP	VNF	AiPO
NAVIGABILITY OF THE RIVER	Provides information on water levels	x	x	x
	Provides detailed information on ice events	x		
	Provides information on congestion on the river	x		x
	Provides information on the technical navigability of the river	x	x	x
	Provides information on the profile of the riverbed	x	x	x
	Plans to maintain inland waterways	x		x
COLLECTION OF CHARGES	Collects charges for the use of inland waterways for the carriage	x	x	
INFRASTRUCTURE	Monitors the status of critical infrastructure	x	x	x
	Monitors the state of the infrastructure	x		x
NAVIGATION DEVICES	Ensures the maintenance and operation of navigational water facilities	x	x	x
INFORMATION SERVICES	Establishes and maintains the Hydroportal and the Central Access Point	x		
	Establishes and maintains the geographic information system		x	
	Establishes and maintains the Central Access Point			x
	Creates the WIR portal - Virtual River Guide	x		
	Feed the EURIS portal		x	x
INVESTMENT SUPERVISION	Accepts notifications and issues water permits	x	x	
	Supervises the implementation of investments in water management	x	x	

Source: Own elaboration

When performing the same tasks related to the process of maintaining the infrastructure, supporting and influencing the transportation process, each management entity is characterized by its own way of operating and often separate procedures for managing and distributing data from the infrastructure. Details of the infrastructure management process can be found in Annex4.

The following is a detailed example of infrastructure management in the French region:

Improving the availability of the river network is a strategic focus for VNF. This ambition is materialized in particular through the implementation of an asset management policy including a specialized preventive maintenance policy, which must constitute a real lever for improving the reliability of network structures and routes, with a view to increase their availability.

Wealth management encompasses the following actions:

- the maintenance of assets (discrete and linear works), i.e. all the technical, administrative and management actions during the life cycle of an asset, intended to maintain it or restore it in a state in which it can perform the required function
- asset monitoring, i.e. the activity, carried out manually or automatically, aimed at observing the actual state of the infrastructure; monitoring differs from inspection in that it is used to assess changes in infrastructure parameters over time; monitoring is an integral part of asset maintenance
- asset inspection, i.e. the compliance check carried out by measuring, observing, testing or calibrating the significant characteristics of the infrastructure
- major maintenance renewal (GER) of heritage, i.e. the action of regenerating part of a piece of equipment or equipment, or the action of major maintenance of long-term equipment of life, carried out with the aim of increasing the life of the good
- assessment of the state of the heritage and its monitoring

Unemployment

Unemployment is the period during which Voies navigables de France carries out maintenance, renovation and modernization work to make the network more reliable and improve the service offer. The annual unemployment program is agreed with users, at local and national level, then proposed for deliberation by the VNF board of directors. The unemployment map is revised each year.

Asset management policy

VNF's asset management policy has in particular materialized through:

- the establishment of a national database of works, aiming at managing, updating and administering in a shared and homogeneous manner the national inventory of infrastructure works and reaches as well as the qualification of their functional state,
- the definition of Preventive Maintenance Plans and associated operating ranges, on the works.

National Books Database

The Works Database (BDO) is an operational and strategic management tool for VNF's infrastructure assets. Its fundamental objective is to capitalize the data of this heritage in a centralized and common tool, shared and harmonized at the national level, in order to:

- quickly have information on one or more works, and regularly updated;
- facilitate access to and sharing of data,
- allow data to be processed to extract useful summaries for analysis or decision support, by structure, by type of structure, by route, by DT, etc.

To fill in this database, and in particular the decomposition and functional state of the structures, a visit method has been developed to:

- assess the state of the functions (example: navigation, maintenance of the body of water, etc.) performed by a structure,
- recommend intervention actions on the structure.

The qualification of the functional state of the works serves as a support for the risk analysis of the works and then for the definition of the policy for prioritizing investment programs at the national level.

The BDO gives a "snapshot" of the knowledge and state of the heritage, according to a harmonized national method. The qualification of the condition of a structure is based on a visual inspection of a structure in operation, and therefore generally in water.

The BDO is based on simple, quick and harmonized visits to the structures with a view to establish the strategy for managing the river infrastructure heritage. It does not dispense with operational management (concrete actions for rehabilitation, maintenance) and regulatory works.

The BDO is neither a work inspection, nor a diagnosis, nor an exhaustive evaluation of the work to be carried out or a CMMS (Computer Aided Maintenance Management). It does not replace the checks and monitoring imposed by regulations or by security requirements.

A Technical Inspection of Works (VTO) is carried out by a person trained in the inventory methodology and qualification of VNF's assets. This person is called Technical Structures Visitor. The Technical Structures Visitor is not necessarily a specialist or expert in all the fields (civil engineering, electromechanical, electricity, etc.) concerned by the visit. For the visit, the Technical Structures Visitor must be if possible (mandatory if external service provider) accompanied by the operator who preferably has a certain knowledge of the structure. The VTO is carried out over a limited period of time (varying from half a day, to 1 or 2 days depending on the complexity and size of the work). It is based on observations (mostly visual) at the time of the visit and on the statements of the operator. During the VTO, no measurements, sampling or tests are carried out. The VTO is not a structural diagnosis. The objective of the VTO is to qualify the functional state of a structure.

Preventive maintenance

Preventive maintenance must allow the maintenance over time of the performance of the structures that the investments in repair will have, if necessary, previously made it possible to improve. It summarizes the components of the management of a given structure by maintenance. It specifies the preventive interventions as well as their parameters (nature, frequency, load, etc.).

The analysis leading to the preventive maintenance plans must take into account all the actions contributing to the maintenance of the structures, independently of the stakeholders (operator, maintainer, external company, etc.), namely:

- routine maintenance of work equipment,
- monitoring and maintenance of current cleanliness,
- routine preventive maintenance, including regulatory actions (particularly related to electrical installations, lifting devices and pressure vessels, etc.),
- major Maintenance and Renewal (GER)

VNF uses MBF method to ensure that preventive maintenance, as the receptacle of a structured preventive approach, guarantees an optimal quality of service when applied scrupulously. The MBF method aims to build a preventive maintenance plan "going to the essentials", from the evaluation of the criticality of the equipment. It is also suitable for optimizing existing preventive maintenance plans, based on the use of feedback. It is completed by an approach to define the so-called "strategic" stock. This is the stock of parts whose unavailability may have consequences deemed "unacceptable" on the quality of service. An MBF analysis aims to size (or specify) the maintenance effort based on the consequences (notions of severity/frequency) of failures (approach by "function") and not according to the failures themselves (approach by "equipment").

"Function" approach: "I maintain the equipment so that it responds correctly to its function"

"The preventive maintenance plan is adapted to the challenge of the equipment"

The MBF is therefore a working method whose result is a preventive maintenance plan, which makes possible to avoid both under-quality and over-quality in maintenance. For a given piece of equipment, a structured preventive maintenance plan contains:

- the preventive maintenance tasks and the periodicities of intervention,
- information on the implementation of these tasks [status of the structure (on/off) to carry out the task, trade concerned, estimated duration of the task and the spare parts required].

The development of preventive maintenance plans is adapted to the scale of a structure.

In general, the scope of a study aimed at producing or optimizing a preventive maintenance plan covers all the equipment of the structure. It is possible that the development of the preventive maintenance plan anticipates scheduled changes to the structure (restoration, replacement of equipment, change of technology, etc.). In this case, it is important to build the preventive maintenance plan by analysing, and also integrating the impact of the changes on the content of the preventive maintenance plan.

The analysis leading to the preventive maintenance plans must take into account all the actions contributing to the maintenance of the structures, independently of the stakeholders (operator, maintainer, external company, etc.), namely:

- Routine maintenance of work equipment,
- Monitoring and maintenance of current cleanliness,
- Routine preventive maintenance, including regulatory actions (particularly related to electrical installations, lifting devices and pressure vessels, etc.),
- Major Maintenance and Renewal (GER*).

* GER: all operations to renew equipment or part of equipment, or major maintenance actions for long-life equipment, carried out with the aim of increasing the life of a good.

An MBF study produces three documents:

- The preventive maintenance plan for a given structure,
- The list of strategic spare parts attached to the structure,
- Actions aimed at improving the reliability of the structure and improving maintenance practices.

The preventive maintenance plan is built on the basis of the expertise of the agents intervening “on a daily basis” on the structure; the technical relevance of the preventive maintenance plan is therefore ensured. The list of strategic spare parts identifies the parts whose unavailability may have consequences deemed "unacceptable" on the quality of service. Finally, the MBF study, based on a criticality analysis, can highlight specific actions to improve the structures or maintenance practices. Updating and optimizing preventive maintenance plans is a continuous process, the MBF is a tool that accompanies the evolution of preventive maintenance plans. Periodic reviews of MBF studies must be undertaken to judge the effectiveness of the preventive maintenance plan and to optimize it again, in a logic of continuous improvement of practices. Optimization is carried out on the basis of feedback, the evolution of the works and the context. However, it is necessary to let the preventive maintenance plans operate long enough, around 2 to 3 years, so that they can bring the benefits of their optimization. It should be noted that the MBF method is not a method to be used in an emergency situation or following a failure. It is a method that focuses on the medium / long term.

The MBF method

The MBF method is based on the following four questions, each corresponding to a method step:

Step 1: How do the facilities work? It is the analysis of the functioning

Sub-step 1.1: find the hardware limits of the studied system

Sub-step 1.2: find the main function(s) of the system

Sub-step 1.3: decomposing the system into Functional Groupings

Step 2: How are the installations malfunctioning? This is the analysis of malfunctions

Sub-step 2.1: Failure Mode

Sub-step 2.2: Detectability

Sub-step 2.3: Effects

- Sub-step 2.4: Pair Maintainable Unit / Cause
- Sub-step 2.5: Criticality
- Sub-step 2.6: Current preventive maintenance

Step 3: How to counter the failures having the most critical consequences? This is the choice of preventive maintenance tasks

- Sub-step 3.1: Maintenance Orientations
- Sub-step 3.2: Choice of maintenance tasks
- Sub-step 3.3: Characterization of proposed tasks

Step 4: How to define the strategic stock of spare parts? This is the determination of the strategic stock

- Lock type breakdown
- Civil engineering - airlock
- Mooring (mooring post, etc.)
- Bajoer
- Chamber door / leaf
- goldfinch
- Coronation
- Access ladder
- Fall wall
- Guard wall
- Surge protector
- Write off
- Civil engineering - upstream or downstream head
- Aqueduct (upstream / downstream / bypass / supply / control / filling ...)
- Level measuring device (limnometric scale, scale level ...)
- Comb
- Pit jacks / rack
- Trailing wall
- Bullnose
- Rock rip-rap
- Portico (light support, cable passage, pipes, etc.)
- Write off
- Guide rails
- Cofferdam grooves
- Stairs
- Platform
- Door
- Joints
- Bridge
- Structure
- Sealing system
- Manoeuvring system
- Lock system
- Airlock filling and emptying system
- Vanes (including manoeuvring system) or valves
- Reach regulation
- Vanes (including manoeuvring system) or valves
- Filling
- Vanes (including manoeuvring system) or valves
- Emptying
- Reach regulation system
- Weir
- Derivation
- Power supply
- Emergency power supply (generator, etc.)
- Transformers
- TGBT / HV cell
- HV/LV distribution
- Cabinet (structure)
- Cabinet (power)
- Cabinet (protection of goods and people)
- Control system (including automation)
- Dedicated backup power (UPS)
- Automaton
- Sensors
- Cabinet (control, relay)
- Communication (cables, cards, ...)

- Telecommunications (telephony, radios, teletransmission, audio, etc.)
- HM interface (touch screen, display, box, control panel)
- User/structure communication system
- Hydraulic central
- Tarpaulin
- Motor pump
- Emergency system (auxiliary electric or manual pump, etc.)
- Control of distribution devices
- Hydraulic distribution
- Piping / Hoses
- Signage, surveillance and security
- Navigation lights
- Information panels
- Navigation panels
- Audible and visual signal
- Video surveillance
- Buoy
- Marking, s on the ground
- Bodyguard
- Means of communication
- PC call intercom
- Radio
- Microphone / HP
- Building
- Shelter, technical room, operating building
- Control cabin
- Place of life
- Lighting
- Building lighting
- Lighting of the work
- Public lighting
- Others
- Dolphins
- Floating body removal device (crane, screen, etc.)
- Site fencing devices

Finally, it should be emphasized that all activities related to the management of river infrastructure, have a direct and indirect impact on the logistics activities using this infrastructure, so it is essential that all actors involved in these processes interact appropriately to ensure smooth, unwavering operation.

3. Identification of main needs and problems affecting IWT

In the evolving landscape of transportation, the chapter "Identification of main needs and problems affecting IWT" serves as a pivotal exploration into the challenges and opportunities that shape the realm of inland waterway logistics. This chapter is dedicated to dissecting the multifaceted needs and complexities intrinsic to the effective operation of waterborne cargo transport systems.

As industries and economies continue to grow, so does the demand for efficient and sustainable modes of transportation. Inland waterway transport, with its potential to alleviate road congestion, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and foster economic growth, stands as a significant player in the global transportation matrix. However, its optimal utilization is often hindered by a web of challenges that demand thoughtful analysis.

The following are the diagnosed main problems and needs faced by stakeholders in the use of IWT in Europe, that affect its efficient utilization:

Infrastructure development: One of the primary needs is the development and maintenance of adequate infrastructure for inland waterways. This includes ensuring sufficient depth, width, and condition of

waterways, as well as modernization and construction of ports, terminals, and locks. Insufficient infrastructure can hinder the smooth flow of goods and passengers, leading to delays and increased costs.

Multimodal connectivity: Stakeholders require improved multimodal connectivity to integrate inland waterways transport seamlessly with other modes of transportation, such as rail and road. Efficient intermodal connections enable the smooth transfer of cargo between different transport modes, enhancing the overall logistics chain. Lack of adequate intermodal infrastructure and coordination can limit the attractiveness and competitiveness of inland waterways transport.

Limited network coverage: Many industrial centers and regions still lack direct access to the waterway network, which hampers the development of a comprehensive and efficient IWT system.

Seasonal limitations: In certain regions, inland waterways can be subject to seasonal limitations due to low water levels during drought periods. Insufficient water depths can restrict vessel navigation and limit the carrying capacity, leading to disruptions in supply chains and reduced reliability of IWT services.

Regulatory framework: Stakeholders need a supportive and harmonized regulatory framework that promotes the use of inland waterways transport. Clear and consistent regulations regarding permits, licensing, safety standards, environmental protection, and customs procedures are necessary for the smooth operation of inland waterway vessels. Inconsistencies in regulations across different countries can create barriers and increase administrative burdens.

Environmental sustainability: There is a growing need for stakeholders to address environmental sustainability concerns. Inland waterways transport is considered a greener alternative to road transport, as it generates lower greenhouse gas emissions and reduces traffic congestion. However, stakeholders must address issues related to water pollution, invasive species, and the ecological impact of infrastructure development to ensure long-term environmental sustainability.

Funding and investment: Adequate funding and investment opportunities are essential for stakeholders to improve and expand inland waterways transport infrastructure. Public and private investments are required for infrastructure upgrades, research and development, and modernization of vessels and equipment. Insufficient funding can hamper the development of the sector and limit its capacity to meet the growing demand.

Collaboration and stakeholder engagement: Stakeholders need to collaborate and engage in constructive dialogue to address common challenges and make informed decisions. This includes cooperation between governments, transport operators, logistics providers, industry associations, and environmental organizations. Lack of coordination and communication among stakeholders can lead to inefficiencies, conflicts of interest, and missed opportunities for improvement.

Limited awareness and promotion: Inland waterways often face a lack of awareness and promotion compared to other transport modes. Greater efforts are needed to showcase the benefits and potential of IWT to logistics providers, shippers, and customers. Promoting IWT as a viable and sustainable transport option can help increase its usage and market share.

Market competitiveness: Stakeholders require a competitive and efficient inland waterways transport market. This involves ensuring fair competition, transparent pricing, and streamlined administrative

procedures. Issues such as limited market access, monopolistic practices, and excessive bureaucracy can hinder the development of a competitive market, reducing the attractiveness of inland waterways transport for shippers and customers.

By addressing these needs and problems, stakeholders can unlock the full potential of inland waterways transport in Europe, promoting its sustainable growth and contributing to a more balanced and environmentally friendly transport system.

Building upon the insights gained from the regional infrastructure analysis, our study identified and prioritized the main needs and problems that hinder the effective use of Inland Waterway Transport within the corridor. These challenges encompassed a wide range of factors, such as outdated infrastructure, inadequate navigational conditions, inefficient intermodal interfaces, and regulatory barriers. The identification of these issues forms the basis for developing targeted solutions and interventions.

Italy - current status and existing challenges

Rivers as natural resource have been used and managed during the centuries in different ways, depending on the specific natural life of the river, on the specific population as well as on their cultural-social-economic history. For example, the hydrographic basin of the Po river, the longest (652 km) Italian river, covers all the north territory of Italy, the most important economic area of Italy, where the 40% of the Italian GDP is created, strongly oriented to the global economy.

The challenges experienced today are mainly the following:

Climate changes impacts (adaptation and mitigation)

- high water (flooding risks) and low water / draughts
- competition of priorities related to management of the water as resource and as transport corridor river
- waterways' infrastructure resilience
- Sustainability and climate change adaptation of private and public organisations involved in IWT

Environmental protection

- biodiversity safeguard, valorisation and restoration;
- water quality improvement and safeguard, based on EC WFD;
- Nature-based (ex. UNESCO Biosphere reserve, natural parks) / Ecosystem based approaches for climate change adaptation;
- Free stream condition restoration, considering geomorphological aspects and approaches;
- Bionomics' aspects, considering new ecological approaches to river restorations (landscape considered as ecosystem);
- Ecosystem services;

Social-economic sustainability

- conflict management of different water uses (energy power plants, agricultural supply, recreational, environment, ...);
- river transport of goods (logistic) and passengers (mobility): e.g. RIS Directive 2005/44/EC adoption from the Italian Sustainable Mobility Ministry, obsolescence of the inland waterways fleets, improvement of the waterways infrastructures, etc.;
- tourism development;
- agriculture resilience;
- land-planning improvement for the resilience of the territories;
- transport, logistic and mobility private Small and Medium Entrepreneurs: lack of knowledge regarding the up-to-date topics : climate change impacts, circular economy, EU-wide classification system for environmentally sustainable economic activities / EU Taxonomy – Sustainable Finance, most CO₂-efficient modes of transport (per tonnes of goods carried) along with rail, Inland Waterway Transport (multi-functional resilient solutions), sustainability and resilience as well as the CO₂-footprint of the supply chains, Business continuity management systems (ISO 22301), etc.;

Governance-related issues:

- support the co-creation processes involving the local stake- and shareholders to support the implementation of sustainable river plan management concerning e.g. the previous topics, implementing and in synergies with:
- EU, national and regional and municipalities' plans regarding water, transport, biodiversity, climate changes, etc (more than 50 local river management plans);
- EU directives and strategies: water, habitat, birds, biodiversity, transport (RIS), green procurement, etc. and Agenda 2030, EU Fit55 and thematic projects like :
- EC H2020 RIS-COMEX www.riscomex.eu/ris-comex/
- Regional directives such as CEF-INIWAS – Improvement of the Northern Italy Waterway System: Removal of physical bottlenecks www.ramspa.it/en/iniwas-0; or CEF WIN-IT, studies and design for the Improvement of the Northern Italy Waterway System, starting soon; etc;
- TEN-T and CEF Corridors;
- EC Blue Economy and EC Green Deal ;
- Sustainable Developments Goals implementation;
- Improvement of the Institutional Capacity of the available capacities in terms of financial means, human capital and technological development allowing for building resilient infrastructures, addressing governance challenges that “cross” administrative boundaries;

A high level overview on the situation of the river partners confirms the relevance of this issues:

Population of the Po area: 19,8 Mio; 86.859 km², 141 feeding rivers, 3.348 municipalities, 8 regional and one province governments, 37% of Italian industrial production, 55% of Italian livestock industry, 35% of Italian agriculture industry, 55% of the Italian hydroelectric production; there is close to no freight transport on the Po river.

Figure 16 Maps of flooding probability areas : P1 = low risk P2= medium risk P3= high risk
Source: www.mite.gov.it

For the Italian river partner the following three dimensions are focal:

- Activation of the Po-river for IWT for freight
- Integration of passenger transport in freight transport concept
- Need for infrastructure and waterlevel early warning systems

France - current status and existing challenges

Interruptions can have serious economic consequences, especially for heavy goods traffic where daily delay penalties are very high; this becomes an even bigger issue when heavy goods traffic is interrupted more often; “ice jams”, e.g. blockages by wood in connection with flooding, cause such serious disruptions and on the Moselle variations in water flow have been observed for the last 5 years. Low water problems on the routes and network occur in particular for smaller vessels with repercussions on the wide-gauge network. Also future consequences for the tourism sector are expected. Real-time monitoring of infrastructure and water depth is therefore crucial. Currently, certain amounts of data is captured already as many sensors are installed on the infrastructures; VNF is working on the issue of connected objects (IoT) and the development of a digital map, and CRISTAL could make it possible to complete this digitalization of infrastructures. As it is expected that climatic events will cause interruptions to traffic, and that difficulties will arise on certain structures, early weather warning systems are important. Furthermore, interfaces to the inclusion of autonomous vessels are needed in the corridor management system, as there is currently no solution in place for them to pass through locks. Furthermore, predictive models that support decision-making processes need to be established and tools for predictive infrastructure maintenance.

Poland - current status and existing challenges

Poland has a significant potential as regards inland waterways. According to the data for 2020 the length of the navigable inland waterways in Poland is 3767.8 km. Only Germany, France, The Netherlands and

Finland have a longer inland waterways in Europe. Also, the density of waterways in Poland higher than the European average¹ with 11.7 km of navigable waterways per 1000 km².

Despite these favorable conditions, the technical quality of inland waterways in Poland is poor and even declining. In 2017, the requirements for waterways of international importance, i.e. at least class IV, were met by only 5.9% of the waterways considered navigable (214 km), in 2018.

The lack of compliance between the actual parameters of the waterway and the parameters defined in the regulation on their classification also poses significant problems.

As a result of the 2017 inventory of inland waterway components in Poland, of the 126 facilities only 24 were involved in transshipments. The degradation of inland waterway transport infrastructure in Poland is primarily the result of:

- the marginalization of inland waterway transport in transport policy,
- low investment in the development and maintenance of inland waterways,
- lack of consistency in the implementation of waterway management programmes,
- complexity of the waterways management system

Limited funds for the development of inland waterways in Poland resulted in inconsistent implementation of waterway development programmes. Also, programmes were not fully implemented, e.g. the cascade of the lower Vistula from the 1960s or the "Programme for the Oder - 2006". Furthermore, during the period 1969-2018, along a 10 km section the water table dropped by 3.62 m due to bottom erosion².

The technical state of inland waterways in Poland is to a large extent a consequence of the complex system of waterway management existing until 2017 and the effect of the exclusion of waterways from the competence of the Ministry of Transport. An orderly and clear definition of management competences, especially with regard to waterways that can potentially be used for transport tasks, can therefore contribute to a more effective implementation of investments improving the condition of inland waterways. A special challenge for the creators of transport policy is the need to convince public opinion, especially certain social groups, of the advisability of carrying out investments on inland waterways. At present a big problem is posed by the circles of "ecologists" who, not knowing the specificity of inland waterway transport and its advantages resulting from the lesser degradation of the environment, often contribute to the formation in public opinion of a negative image of inland waterway transport and, as a result, contribute to the effective blocking of investments on waterways. An example of such a situation can be seen in the problems related to the construction of the Siarzewo barrage downstream of the Włocławek barrage. Despite the fact that in 2017 this investment was approved by the Economic Committee of the Council of Ministers for implementation, and despite the fact that a positive environmental decision was issued, this decision was protested by organizations of "environmentalists". Since 2017, the decision resolving this dispute is delayed every few months. In this light, it is important to popularize knowledge in the society about the specificity of inland waterway transport and the benefits that are associated with the development of inland waterways.

¹ Own calculations based on: Statistical pocketbook 2021, EU Transport in figures, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg 2021, https://ec.europa.eu/transport/facts-fundings/statistics/pocketbook-2021_en[accessed: 16.09.2021].

² Z. Babiński, M. Habel, 50 years of research on the Vistula riverbed below the Włocławek reservoir together with forecast for the coming years, "Gospodarka Wodna" 2020, no. 10.

CRISTAL and regional pilot sites therefore addresses the following key issues:

Navigational issues: IWT must cope with varying water levels limiting ship payloads due to insufficient air draught under bridges and raised transport costs at low water. Volatile water levels and ever-changing riverbed conditions impede optimal river navigation and cause time losses.

Waterways infrastructures resilience issues: engineering standards must be addressed, maintenance and procurement rules and the governance challenges that “cross” administrative boundaries; new infrastructure must be built considering life-cycle use optimization and environmental impact minimization to ensure long-term sustainability and economic validity.

Environmental issues: biodiversity safeguard, water quality improvement and safeguard, as well as free stream condition restoration need to be integral part of IWT improvements, considering geomorphological aspects and approaches such as bionomics as well as new ecological approaches to river restorations (landscape considered as ecosystem).

Socio-economic issues: conflict management of different water uses (energy power plants, agricultural supply, recreational, environment, ...) need to be addressed; river transport for goods (logistic) and for passengers (mobility) need to be coordinated, and governance structures are needed, that support the co-creation processes, involving the local stakeholders, to support the implementation of sustainable corridor management plan.

In order to improve the resilience and reliability of IWT and to shift transport to this transport mode, new approaches are needed today. Climate changes’ impacts, globalization of economies and more recent tendencies to protectionism and closed frontiers, also pandemic induced, technological developments and digitalization as well as the demand for sustainable financial markets (making easy access to funding and financing for climate-prepared infrastructure and fleet as well as logistic and transport services) render innovative approaches necessary and possible.

Best practices are surely available at local level but these best practices must in short and long time term be evaluated regarding the on-going and expected global changes of the climate and the cascade effects for the local and national society.

Managing the river risks, produced by the concurrent combination of natural, economic, social and governance factors is today and even more in the future more complicated and risky than before, because practically each possible solution must consider and evaluate all the physical, environmental, organizational, socio-economic, cascade effects and the direct–indirect costs.

Consequently, all relevant capacities (ecologist, engineers, supply chain managers, tourism and cultural operators, public and civil protection planners, river authorities, politics, NGOs – citizens organization, etc.) must take the responsibility to become and to act as „part of the solution“ and NOT as „part of the problem“. The goal is smart, green, sustainable and climate-resilient IWT, planned in a way that maximizes positive impact on economic growth and minimizes negative impact on the environment and, significant and lasting degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats, promoting environmentally friendly modes of transport and leading to the reduction of transport emissions.

4. Factors affecting the resilience of the infrastructure

Considering one of the main objectives of the project, achieving resilience of river infrastructure involves implementing strategies and measures to enhance the infrastructure's ability to withstand and recover from disruptions, adapt to changing conditions, and maintain functionality over the long term. The following identifies the main areas that are responsible for the increase in river infrastructure and that will be taken into account when creating scenarios for the implementation of the pilots:

Risk assessment and management:

- Conduct a comprehensive risk assessment to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities to river infrastructure, such as floods, erosion, climate change impacts, and accidents.
- Develop risk management plans that outline strategies to mitigate identified risks, including protective measures, early warning systems, emergency response protocols, and contingency plans.

Adequate design and construction:

- Ensure that river infrastructure, such as locks, bridges, embankments, and ports, is designed and constructed to withstand foreseeable risks and stresses, including extreme weather events and changing water levels.
- Consider climate change projections and future scenarios when designing and building new infrastructure or retrofitting existing structures.

Regular maintenance and inspections:

- Establish and implement a robust maintenance program to ensure the continuous functionality and structural integrity of river infrastructure.
- Conduct regular inspections and assessments to detect and address maintenance needs, including routine inspections, non-destructive testing, and condition monitoring.

Enhanced safety measures:

- Implement safety measures to protect infrastructure, personnel, and users. This may include safety protocols, signage, navigational aids, and equipment upgrades.
- Educate and train personnel on safety procedures and emergency response plans to ensure a swift and coordinated response in case of incidents or accidents.

Climate change adaptation:

- Assess the potential impacts of climate change on river systems, including changes in water levels, increased frequency of extreme weather events, and altered flow patterns.
- Implement adaptation measures to minimize vulnerabilities and enhance the resilience of river infrastructure, such as adjusting designs, improving flood protection measures, and promoting nature-based solutions.

Collaboration and stakeholder engagement:

- Foster collaboration among stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, waterway operators, environmental organizations, and researchers.
- Engage stakeholders in decision-making processes, exchange knowledge and expertise, and develop joint strategies for infrastructure resilience and sustainable river management.

Data and monitoring:

- Establish a robust data collection and monitoring system to gather information on water levels, flow rates, sediment transport, infrastructure performance, and environmental conditions.
- Use collected data to assess the effectiveness of resilience measures, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions for infrastructure management and planning.

Long-term planning and investment:

- Develop long-term plans and investment strategies for the maintenance, repair, and modernization of river infrastructure.
- Allocate adequate resources and funding to implement resilience measures, including regular maintenance, infrastructure upgrades, and capacity-building initiatives.

Environmental considerations:

- Incorporate environmental considerations into infrastructure planning and management to ensure sustainable and ecosystem-friendly practices.
- Promote sustainable river management approaches, such as habitat restoration, sediment management, and water quality improvement, to support the overall resilience of the river ecosystem.

By implementing changes in the above areas at the corridor level, river infrastructure can be made more resilient, capable of withstanding and adapting to various challenges and ensuring the continuous and efficient functioning of waterway systems supporting logistics activities.

5. IWT disruptions

Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) can face various disruption events that may affect the smooth flow of cargo and transportation operations. These disruptions can arise from natural factors, technical issues, regulatory changes, or other unforeseen circumstances. Working with partners in the pilot regions, we were able to define a set of major, most common disruptions that affect both infrastructure and operations at the logistics level:

Natural disruptions: Floods or surges, adverse weather phenomena (fog, storms), and low water levels can affect waterway navigation, causing delays and potential closures.

Infrastructure and maintenance issues: Maintenance work on the shipping lane, inoperable infrastructure facilities (e.g., damage to the canal bottom, closure due to fortuitous events like bridge

failures or military maneuvers), and lack of availability of the barge before transport can lead to schedule disruptions.

Cargo-related disruptions: Damage to cargo during transportation, loss of cargo during carriage, and unfavorable movement of material on the bottom of the shipping lane can lead to cargo losses, delays, and environmental hazards.

Human-related disruptions: Breakdown/non-availability of personnel or handling equipment, strikes by port workers, and lack of competent staff to operate or maintain infrastructure can impact cargo handling and vessel operations.

Vessel-related disruptions: Failure of a barge during a voyage, barge sinking, and stranding of the barge can result in cargo losses, safety risks, and navigational challenges.

Security and protest-related disruptions: Protest by environmental organizations, technological incidents (hazardous materials transport, explosions in logistic centers/industries), and water pollution can cause disruptions and safety concerns.

Unforeseen events: Unexpected random events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, can lead to travel restrictions, workforce shortages, and supply chain disruptions.

Congestion and delays: Congestion at terminals and ports, vehicle delays due to traffic congestion, or delays in previously executed orders can result in shipment delays and logistical challenges.

IT failures and cybersecurity: IT failures and cybersecurity breaches can disrupt digital systems, affecting communication, documentation, and tracking in the transportation process.

A detailed breakdown of the disruptions worked out with the Pilots is presented in Annex0.

To manage these potential disruptions effectively, stakeholders in the IWT industry must implement contingency plans, maintain constant communication, and have flexible operational strategies in place. Regular maintenance and investment in infrastructure are essential to ensure the safety and efficiency of inland waterway transportation. As part of the CRISTAL project, additional support for the planning and organization of logistics processes through the SCMS (Synchromodal Corridor Management System) tool, will help mitigate the risks and reduce the impact of their occurrence within the corridor.

6. Determination of baseline and test definition

To establish a baseline for performance assessment and measure the impact of potential improvements, we defined the existing state of the corridor in terms of various performance indicators. This baseline assessment involved the collection and analysis of relevant data to benchmark the current performance levels and identify areas for improvement. Drawing from this baseline, we formulated a comprehensive set of tests that leverage new technologies and concepts to overcome the challenges identified earlier. These tests were designed to evaluate the efficacy of innovative solutions in enhancing the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of IWT operations within the corridor. The following sections provide pilot

scenarios for all three regions taking into account their objectives, actors, technologies and the KPIs by which results will be measured.

6.1. Italian pilot

6.1.1. River Pilot Goals

The Italian river pilot aims at enhancing and promoting the navigability on the Po river, which is located in northern Italy.

More specifically, the goal of the pilot is, in line with the CRISTAL project view, to find innovative technological solutions for monitoring the river infrastructure and to facilitate the transport processes in order to support the development of businesses that can benefit from an improved inland waterway transport (IWW) infrastructure. In practice, the target is to increase the reliability and the level of service of the navigability on the Po river.

Figure 17 The Po river system

Source: <https://mobilita.regione.emilia-romagna.it/settore-idroviario/doc/idroviaferrarese/english-version/the-waterway-of-ferrara-in-europe/submissions-for-cef-funding>

In detail, the main objectives of the Italian river pilot are the following:

1. Improvement of the asset management of the inland waterways' infrastructure, taking into account new technologies and the environmental impacts;
2. Testing innovative technologies for forecasting the navigability conditions and studying the implementation of cold-ironing facilities along the quays;
3. Innovation and improvement of the governance process supporting activities like: route planning, transport and traffic management, securing the supply for goods for the relevant supply chain and for tourism management;

4. Digitalization of the logistic and of the people transport services (multimodality and a synchro modality perspective);
5. Reduction of the CO₂ footprint of the river management services and support of the “Business continuity management” of the transport services.

For these purposes the following technologies will be tested:

- Fiber Optic Sensing (FOS) technology, functionalized with weighing pads: for the permanent monitoring of critical section lines of free-flowing waterways
- New Hydraulic/statistic model: for depth evaluation and navigation availability
- New smart daily report: for forecasting the navigability in the different section of the Po river (based on the correlation between discharge and draught)
- Cold ironing: a feasibility study for the realization of a network of cold ironing facilities
- Acoustic monitoring of a lock door³: for checking the good operation status of a lock door

Two of the main partners of the projects are Infrastrutture Venete Srl (IV) and Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po (AIPo), which will focus on the following actions:

- IV – Within Task 7.2, IV is in particular tackling the analysis and planning of a potential network of cold ironing facilities to be realized along the Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante e Po – Brondolo channels, in the North-East part of Italy. The main goal will be to transfer to other IWW infrastructure managers, a structured approach and methodology to be used in order to plan the upgrade of IWW by providing easy-to-use and interconnected charging points/stations supporting the alternative prolusion of inland navigation, thus following the main course of EU strategy on transport targeting low carbon emissions transport system in the next future.
- AIPo – Within Task 7.2, AIPo Engineering and implementation of a forecasting navigability model. This task will realize a hydraulic/statistic model using observed and mid term forecasted data at +5 and +10 days. Within 7.3 AIPo will implement a Corridor management and organizational model for sustainability, resilience and competitiveness of the territorial synchro modal transport system.

6.1.2. Pilot Case Specification

“Padano-Veneta” inland waterway transport infrastructure

In Italy, the realisation of the “Padano-Veneta” inland waterway has been recognised of strategic and priority importance at national level with the law 380/1990. The realisation of the inland waterway was responsibility of the Italian Transport Ministry, in collaboration with the Regions crossed by the planned inland waterway.

³ This technology will be developed by CERTH as part of WP5 (task 5.2)

The transport network and infrastructure of the “Padano-Veneta” inland waterway (the inland waterways in Northern Italy and the Northern Adriatic) consists of (moving progressively from west to east along the Po Valley):

- the inland ports of Cremona, Mantua, Rovigo, Boretto, Ferrara and Porto Nogaro (and other public and private docks along the waterway);
- the Po River (from Piacenza to river mouth) and the Mantua-Adriatic Sea Canal (Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante), i.e. the two main waterways that synergistically connect the sea to the heart of the Po Valley, with an east-west relationship, where the inland ports are located;
- the Po-Brondolo canal;
- the Ferrara waterway;
- the Venice Lagoon;
- the Litoranea veneta waterway;
- the North Adriatic Sea ports, such as Ravenna, Chioggia, Venice, Monfalcone and Trieste.

The Italian pilot on the Po river focuses on the following IWW sections:

- Po river from Cremona to Mantua;
- Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante;
- Po - Brondolo.

In Italy, the Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure is responsible for the construction and management of inland waterways, while the Regions are responsible for regulating inland navigation and managing inland waterways in their respective territories. The Regions have an agreement with an infrastructure operator for the exercise of some inland navigation functions. The Regions involved with the Padano-Veneta waterway are Piedmont, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Veneto and Friuli-Venezia Giulia. The first four Regions signed an agreement, the “Interregional agreement for navigation on the river Po”, in order to distribute the competences and the funds (also from the Government) destined for inland navigation among the participants in the agreement. As the Italian pilot focuses on some sections of the Padano-Veneta waterway (i.e. the section Cremona – “foce Mincio” (Mincio mouth) and the section Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal), the reference Regions are Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna and Veneto. Each of these three Regions signed an “Agreement” with an inland waterway infrastructure operator for pooling in the exercise of inland navigation functions. In particular, Lombardy and Emilia-Romagna have delegated the Interregional Agency for the Po River (Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po (A.I.Po)), the responsibility of realising and maintaining the necessary infrastructures to ensure the free flow navigation (groynes) along the Po river from the delta to the city of Piacenza (to which the Cremona – “foce Mincio” section belongs). Furthermore, AIPo manages the functioning of different navigation locks along the Po river and the Lombardy reaches of the Fissero-Tartaro-Canalbianco system. Veneto Region identified Infrastrutture Venete (IV) as the operator of the regional inland navigation network (that includes the Fissero - Tartaro - Canalbianco - Po di Levante canal and Po – Brondolo canal) and also, since January 1st 2020, of the regional railway infrastructures. Therefore, IV manages the system of locks and hydraulic supports that compose the Veneto internal navigation network, is responsible for dredging the inland waterways, and has also a mediation/coordination role with several other institutions of the territory that have to be coordinated, e.g. for the management of mobile bridges. Both Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po and Infrastrutture Venete are two project partners.

Regarding the “planning” side, for flood protection and water resources management, the activities are coordinated by District Authorities, established after the Water Framework Directive, and the Padano-Veneta inland waterway falls within the territory of the Po river District Authority and the Eastern Alps District Authority.

Navigation infrastructures along the Po river must be planned and realized in coherence and accordance with flood risk mitigation objectives, set out in the Po district Flood Risk Management Plan, and with environmental objectives, defined in the Po River Basin Management Plan, as required by the Flood Directive 2006/60/CE, and the Water Directive 2000/60/CE.

Design of navigation infrastructures along the Po river must be approved by the Po river district Authority, that has to verify their environmental and safety compatibility.

Inland navigation management is under the duties of the Italian Ministry for Transport and Infrastructures, while District Authorities respond directly to the Italian Ministry for the Environment and Energetic Safety, and coordinate regional activities related to water resources protection and flood risk mitigation.

Cremona-Mantua (infrastructure operator: AIPo)

AIPo will focus instead on allowing an adequate planning of navigation activities on the sections by the various users, considering the logistical and travel problems, having tools available that can provide useful information on the navigability of the sections, even in forecast, as it is essential for correct planning and as an incentive to investments in the sector.

The data currently available are:

- cartographic data of shallow waters and navigable sections;
- datasets measured on shallow waters collected by the navigation area from about 1988 until today on the main known critical points
- historical flow and level data to the hydrometers present
- flow prediction provided by numerical water management models (DEWS)

Figure 18 River infrastructure managed by AIPo

Source: Own elaboration

Pausing for simplicity to analyse the heights recorded in relation to the flow rate, it is possible to observe a strong correlation between flow rate and tie rod, in which the variations of the tie rod with the same flow rate can be ascribed to both natural and artificial bathymetric variations, as well as more general variations in the morphology of the watercourse and consequent migration of the bottom shapes and of the same incised riverbed.

The process will be focused on models capable to carry out a correlation between the water level data, the flow rates recorded for each station and critical points depth, should be possible to identify, on the basis of the available historical data, a statistical index related to "navigability" of the section as a function of the flow rate and the necessary draft.

By applying these "historical" analyses to the forecast data, it is therefore possible to associate a probability of navigability of the shallow water to each expected flow.

Finally, by applying this analysis to all the shallow waters present in a stretch and considering the probability of the stretch equal to the minimum probability of the shallow waters present, it is possible to identify an indicator for each stretch of river.

The output of these analysis represents the input for RIS and for the Cristal synchro modal platform.

Fissero-Po di Levante and Po-Brondolo canals (infrastructure operator: Infrastrutture Venete)

Infrastrutture Venete Srl will focus its analysis along two main branches of the IWW currently managed and represented by the following images:

Figure 19 Fissero – Tartaro – Canalbianco – Po di Levante canal
Source: Own elaboration

Figure 20 Brondolo canal
Source: Own elaboration

Both of these branches are part of the Core and Comprehensive network of the TEN-T, within the Mediterranean Corridor as evidenced in the following figure taken from the TEN-Tech map viewer of the EC.

Figure 21 Overview of the area identified within the TEN-T network

Source: Own elaboration

The overall management of such infrastructures is also including the need to take into consideration the management of more than 30 navigation locks (i.e. *conche di navigazione*), several piers and slides (i.e. *pontili e scivoli*) as well as both fix and mobile bridges that area allowing the full exploitation of the waterway.

The waterway is exploiting the connectivity of important areas of the territory of Veneto Region, thus allowing to directly interconnect the Adriatic Sea with inland areas that are easily reachable through inland navigation.

Such branches of the IWW are then directly managed by Infrastrutture Venete Srl in collaboration with the local Inspectorates (i.e. *ispettorati di porto*) which are contributing to the regulation in the use of such infrastructure.

Stakeholders

See Deliverable D4.1 “Detailed requirements for the governance framework”, Table 8 (page 23).

Traffic information

See Deliverable D1.1 “Domain Map, Vision Statement and Requirements”, Figure 9 (page 19).

6.1.3. Pilot Actors & Involved Systems/Technologies/Infrastructure

Pilot actors

The following table is taken from Deliverable D4.1 “Detailed requirements for the governance framework”, Table 7 (page 22).

Table 3 Pilot actors (Italy)

	Main actors	Detailed actors	Italian Case
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		IWT	AIPO Infrastrutture Venete
	Transport companies		
		Barge operators	
	Tech provider		
		Supplier 1 of technology	ENEA (Fiber Optic, FO sensors)
	Supplier 2 of technology	CERTH (Acoustic Emission)	
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	
		Country government	
		Local government (Regional)	
		Basin Authorities	
Other	Sector organisations representing private companies		Camere di commercio, Unioncamere and Uniontransporti
	Linked industries		Sogesca

Source: Own elaboration

Systems/ Technologies/ Infrastructure involved in pilot case

Fiber Optic Sensing (FOS)

FOS technology will be used to measure the strain levels due to the additional sediment on the bottom of the river in some critical sections in order to estimate the volume and the height of the sediments.

New hydraulic/statistic model

AIPO will contribute to CRISTAL activities by developing a forecasting navigability model. This task will realize a hydraulic model implemented using DEWS (Drought Early Warning System) data of discharge, observed, and forecasted at +5 and +10 days. The detailed definition of the technologies to be developed and installed in this purpose is part of the expected outcomes of the study to be carried out. Analysing

the data related to the discharges it will be possible to perform an evaluation of the depth and the navigation availability.

New smart daily report

Considering historical data set of draught and discharge coupled with depth and navigation forecasting time series the daily report will forecast the navigability in the different section of the Po river (based on the correlation between discharge and draught).

The activity to be carried out by AIPo will address the challenge of providing effective decision support for the main stakeholders in order to reduce the uncertainty due to the free flowing settlement of the Po River and climate change. AIPo will focus on the development of a forecast bulletin in order to provide information on the navigability conditions of the Po river in order to predict or not, within the supply chain, the transport of goods by river.

Cold ironing

Infrastrutture Venete Srl will contribute to CRISTAL activities by delivering a feasibility study testing the possibility to develop a dedicated network of cold ironing facilities along the two branches of the IWW managed and already reported above. The detailed definition of the technologies to be developed and installed in this purpose is part of the expected outcomes of the study to be carried out.

The feasibility study to be carried out by Infrastrutture Venete Srl will face the challenge of providing alternative supply of (renewable) energy to equip the IWW with a new network of charging points. In this purpose, the new infrastructure will be ready to receive innovative boost as well as to fully follow the main addressee of the EU Commission on the future of decarbonized transport. IV will focus on the topic of energy supply to boats using the waterway and in particular on the possibility to develop a dedicated supporting infrastructure to provide both renewable energy production at local level and an adequate typology of devices to be used for charging e-boats or for plug-in services for boats. Details of such technologies are going to be the focus of the feasibility study to be carried out within CRISTAL.

Acoustic Emission monitoring

The AE monitoring is a cooperation of the Italian pilot project with WP5 in line with what reported in Task 7.5: "support to WP5 will be provided to identify which kind of data are needed in order to deliver concrete and useful answers to the develop DSS (Decision Support System) able to enhance the overall management of Po River IWW".

Through the analysis of acoustic emission (AE) data, it will be possible to check the good operational status of a lock door.

The project activity consists in the installation of the CERTH AE system in two locks (Isola Serafini, Baricetta) along the Po river to do some measurements. AIPo and IV will support CERTH to identify where to install the systems and to access the selected sites for measurements.

CERTH will gather and process the data and will directly coordinate with the Digital Twin (WP5) for the expected developments. For this reason, the AE topic won't be further discussed in the rest of the document.

6.1.4. Pilot Execution Plan

Fiber Optic Sensing

The testing phases for the Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS) will follow a three-step path, namely:

Step I – Desk Study, TRL⁴ 1-3

This phase consists of a desk study of the FOS sensors, to qualitatively analyse the functionality of:

- the FOS sensors to support the monitoring of sand dunes movement in the Po river bed;
- the proposed metric, referred to as Performance Indicators (PI), identified with the strain measured by the FOS;
- the analytical model allowing to estimate the sand dune height and shape from the PI measured by the FOS.

This qualitative assessment may be guided and performed through an innovation questionnaire or an ad-hoc workshop. The expected result from this first step is to gain a clear description of the intended functionality of the FOS sensors (e.g., design criteria), the identification of possible failure modes, a preliminary theoretical social acceptance assessment, and an initial screening of the potential impact of the innovation on different sectors pertinent to IWW.

Step II – Laboratory Testing, TRL 4-5

In this phase the FOS is analysed based on the design criteria identified during the Desk Study. Laboratory testing of the technical PI is performed and, for those impacts that require further testing, simple semi-quantitative or more detailed qualitative evaluation of impacts is performed. A preliminary social acceptance check will be completed which may be based on interactions with representative stakeholder groups.

Step III – Operational Testing, TRL 6-8

In this phase the innovation is analysed using the boundary conditions associated with the (intended) operational and market environment. This phase consists of analysing the PI under operational boundary conditions, and demonstrating the performance of the innovation when placed in a simulated operational environment and/or during real events. A more detailed impact assessment may be conducted using the existing conditions at the location. Social acceptance testing may be performed with stakeholders or end-

⁴ Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are different points on a scale used to measure the progress or maturity level of a technology. The scale ranges from 1 to 9, where TRL 1 is the lowest and TRL 9 is the highest. When a technology is at TRL 1, scientific research is beginning and those results are being translated into future research and development, while at TRL 9 the technology has already been proven to work

users from the environment where the innovation is intended to be implemented. These tests represent a significant step in demonstrating the technical effectiveness and social readiness of the innovation.

The following simplified GANTT is providing an overview of the expected timeline to develop the abovementioned foreseen activities.

Table 4 Implementation plan - Italy

FOS development – activities	Start Date	End Date	Corresponding CRISTAL milestone
Desk Study	01/09/2022	28/02/2024	MS4
Laboratory Testing	01/03/2024	30/08/2024	MS5
Operational Testing	01/09/2024	28/02/2025	MS6

Table 5 Gantt chart - Italy

	feb-23	mar-23	apr-23	mag-23	giu-23	lug-23	ago-23	set-23	ott-23	nov-23	dic-23	gen-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	mag-24	giu-24	lug-24	ago-24	set-24	ott-24	nov-24	dic-24	gen-25	feb-25	
Desk Study	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█													
Laboratory Testing														█	█	█	█	█	█	█						
Operational Testing																					█	█	█	█	█	█

Hydraulic model and new smart daily report

In order to allow an adequate planning of navigation activities on the sections by the various users, considering the logistical and travel problems, having tools available that can provide useful information on the navigability of the sections, even in forecast, is essential for correct planning and as an incentive to investments in the sector.

Step I – Data

The data currently available are:

- Cartographic data of shallow waters and navigable sections;
- Datasets measured on shallow waters collected by the navigation area from about 1988 until today on the main known critical points
- Historical flow and level data to the hydrometers present
- Flow prediction provided by numerical water management models

Step II – Hydraulic and/or statistical modelling

Step III – Shallow water navigability prediction model

Step IV – Navigability bulletin of river stretches

Step V – Study of the possibility of integrating the navigability bulletin into the RIS Italy

Step VI – Integration of navigability bulletin data into Cristal Synchronodal platform

Cold Ironing

The overall commitment of Infrastrutture Venete Srl within the Cristal pilot is represented by the development of a feasibility study on the development of cold ironing facilities along the IWW.

More in particular such studies are going to be organized as follows:

Step I – Currently launched, a dedicated assignment will be organized in order to identify an external expert in charge of:

- Developing the tendering procedures for the technical activities of study;
- Following and coordinating such studies
- Reporting the results of the studies according to the templates/requests of the CRISTAL project
- Confronting and giving feedbacks to other WPs with reference to the results of the studies and of the activities carried out.

Step II – To be launched and activated in April 2023 an assignment for external expert/subcontractor in charge of developing the feasibility study aimed at understanding:

- how to plan the installation of cold ironing points along IV's waterway, taking into consideration not only its performance characteristics and the infrastructure as a whole, but also
- the potential derived from the possible use of renewable energies that are able to adequately power the cold ironing infrastructures to be created, in full synergy with the territories crossed by the infrastructure.

Moreover, the assignment should also provide for the definition of a sort of logical framework to be used for the choice of whether or not to make this type of investment in a given point according to the specifics of that point analysed through the tool/logic proposed by the feasibility study.

This last activity will represent a strong added value for the project itself which will be able to deliver a tool to efficiently spread the specific knowledge gained in other territories/context.

Step III – To be launched and activated in October 2023 an assignment for external expert/subcontractor in charge of developing the design of a "typical plant" model of cold ironing facility.

This activity will be necessarily launched once part of the analysis activity referred to in the above point has been clarified / deepened. It will be an activity that will be played in parallel with that of the point above, and the possible complementarity with respect to other specific initiatives launched by Infrastrutture Venete Srl will also be verified into detail.

The following simplified GANTT is providing an overview of the expected timeline to develop the activities foreseen.

Table 6 Gantt chart – Italy 2

	feb-23	mar-23	apr-23	mag-23	giu-23	lug-23	ago-23	set-23	ott-23	nov-23	dic-23	gen-24	feb-24	mar-24	apr-24	mag-24	giu-24	lug-24	ago-24	set-24	ott-24	nov-24	dic-24	gen-25	feb-25
Assignment 1	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Assignment 2			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
Assignment 3									█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

6.1.5. Expected Pilot Results & Assessment Plan

This section outlines the key performance indicators that will be scrutinized to gauge the effectiveness and success of the testing phase. By meticulously detailing the assessment framework, this chapter lays the foundation for an informed evaluation of the pilot's impact:

Table 7 Italian pilot KPIs

Proposed KPIs	This KPI will be measured by- test or simulation	What technology is this KPI related to	Measuring data
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
ENV5-PM (µg/m3)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
ENV6-GHG as CO2e (tonnes of CO2e / tkm)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing</p>

			<p>implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (toe /tkm)	estimate	cold ironing	<p>The feasibility study is evaluating the potential impact of cold ironing implementation.</p> <p>Data referred to: - Fissero-Tartaro-Canal Bianco</p> <p>A possible generalization to the whole IWW could be implemented through the Living Lab</p>
S1-Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines	estimate	- cold ironing - Forecast model (output: smart bulletin)	<p>Through the Living Lab, new governance models will be evaluated.</p> <p>For the cold ironing, the feasibility study will develop the implementation plan.</p>
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	test	Forecast model (output: smart bulletin)	Questionary/Tests with the involvement of the Living Lab
ITA 1_Users Reservation of Navigation Lock by Multimodal Platform	test	Multimodal platform (DT Smart Monitor)	Number of reservations
ITA2 Navigation Bulletin downloads	test	Multimodal platform (DT Smart Monitor)	Counter on the web site/service
ITA 3 Registered users	test	Multimodal platform (DT Smart Monitor)	Number of subscriptions
ITA 4_Navigation forecast points along the river	test	Forecast model (output: smart bulletin)	Number of forecast points

6.2. French pilot

6.2.1. River Pilot Goals

Objectives

- Securing revenue linked to tolls for goods and reduction of costs linked to the process of collecting and checking travel data, thanks to the collection of data from chargers
- Geolocate barges and know the availability of parking and handling areas
- Improve maintenance (the pilot will test a technology developed in WP2 to improve maintenance)

6.2.2. Pilot Case Specification

The French pilot is made up of two sites : the Seine downstream and the Moselle

Figure 22 Location of the rivers - the Seine downstream and the Moselle
Source Own elaboration

Seine downstream

The Seine is a strategic fluvial axis which connects the first national port complex (HAROPA with the ports of Le Havre, Rouen and Paris) to the Ile-de-France region, the largest French conurbation and one of the largest in Europe. River traffic today contributes significantly to the transport of goods within this major

economic area, whether it be construction materials, agricultural products, energy products, various containerized goods, transport of waste, vehicles or heavy packages.

However, its use could be greatly strengthened. In fact, as an unsaturated transport infrastructure, the Seine would be able to have 4 times more traffic than it has today. Indeed it presents a credible and ecologically virtuous alternative to road freight transport and constitutes a major asset for reinforcing the positions of the ports of the Seine axis and developing their hinterland.

With 233km long between Rouen and Paris, the Seine is a large-gauge class Vb river (European classification of waterways), open to 24 hour navigation: it can allow 185 meters long barges which carry up to 5,000 tonnes of goods, the equivalent of 250 trucks. On average, between 10,000 and 16,000 ships go annually through the locks of the Seine, 85% of which are freight ships.

Traffic is enabled thanks to a high level of service (physical and digital service) but it needs to be improved to meet the multifunctionality of the waterway. Maintaining the downstream Seine axis under minimum performance conditions should make possible to continue to perform the two main functions of the river, namely navigation and hydraulic management.

Maintaining these two functions requires, in particular, a good structural and operating condition of the infrastructure, but also real-time monitoring, short-term operational forecasting and coordinated and optimized management of traffic, structures and water levels.

Figure 23 Seine river
Source Own elaboration

Figure 24 Bassin de la Seine
Source Own elaboration

Moselle downstream

The large gauge Moselle (class V) running over 152 km allows the passage of self-propelled and pushed convoys of more than 3,000 tons to the North Sea ports via the Rhine. Other waterways of Freycinet gauge and accessible to commercial navigation converge towards the Moselle, thus having a possible role of feeder lanes. It directly serves two major cities (Metz and Nancy), the industrial basins of Thionville, Pont-à-Mousson and the Saar basin. It has public and private ports, including the port of Metz (9th in France with 2,183,000 tonnes in 2019).

Floods can indirectly impact navigation with hazards such as ice jams or landings, as well as movement of markings. These hazards also generate disturbances. The number of phenomena impacting navigation remains constant from 3 to 4 per year. The possible flood period also tends to extend.

Measures are taken during the low water period: from beginning of July to end of October (or even December). VNF has always faced difficulties in regulating flows on the Moselle. Indeed, for low to medium flows, flow waves are observed propagating upstream to downstream of the Moselle.

The regulation for both dams and hydroelectric plants consists of maintaining as closely as possible the regulation level set upstream of each dam. This mode of regulation does not make possible to reduce the flow waves, in some cases it even accentuates them. The mode of operation can accentuate wave phenomena: this is largely due to problems of interactions between dams and hydroelectric power stations over which VNF has no control (unlike our German or Luxembourg counterparts which are also

police and regulatory authority for hydroelectricity). Regulation taking into account an improvement in flow regulation will lead to a greater tidal range around the regulation level upstream of the dams.

For each reach, in addition to the already formalized ‘target’ regulation range, a maximum admissible high and low level for the level upstream of the dams should be defined. These ratings would take into account the needs for navigation, ie the minimum draught for ships below bridges and the channel depth for ship draught.

Figure 25 Voies navigables - VNF

Source Own elaboration

Logistic

In most cases, clients are shippers from various industries, purchasing transportation services from ship-owners, but more often through charterers, whose job is to find out barges available at the right time and location. This way of proceeding regards a wide range of industries such as: sand and gravels, grain, bulk waste, breakbulk cargo, etc.

In this sort of business, other companies may act as purchasers of IWT as well. They are in direct contact with a client, and instead of restricting their service to their own know-how (stevedoring) they sometimes offer a port to port service (meaning they charter barges on a single voyage or tonnage basis) or even sometimes door to door.

This practically means that barges are the property of three possible profiles:

- In most cases, barge owners (who own 1 to 4 barges as an individual, but this number may reach several hundred in some cases),
- In more particular cases, in specific industries such as sand & gravel production where logistics costs are a key point, producers may own a few dozens of barges and a few pushers (in France, there are two such companies owning, each of them, around one hundred barges and about ten pushers),
- Finally, due to lack of barges available (especially in the current context in Europe) some shippers choose to invest in their own fleet. VNF operates a subsidies program providing them with financial support for such purchases.

Containers are carried on inland waterways by containers barging operators, who charter barges from shipowners, mostly on a time charter basis, in order to offer port to port services with regular schedules. In some cases, those containers barging operators own their own barges, but this is rather seldom. In the same way, city distribution barging services are managed by multimodal freight forwarders, who most of the time charter the barges but in some cases may also own them, and include in their services final km delivery, nearly always with cargo e-bikes.

Traffic

As a result of the health crisis, the 2020 results for river freight activity show a drop of – 10.7% in tonnes, i.e. 50.9 million tonnes transported and – 11.6% in t-km, i.e. nearly 6.6 billion tonne-kilometres (t-km). The river dynamic initiated in 2019 (+10.0 in t-km) was slowed down by the health crisis. However, maintaining its 2018 level, and compared to other modes of transport, the change remains weak, demonstrating the resilience and adaptability demonstrated by the river sector. In 2021, river traffic is up by 3.8% in t-km over the year compared to 2020. Despite the ongoing crisis, traffic exceeds the level of 2018 (+1.1% in t-km).

Traffic volumes on the French pilot sites have been for the past twenty years relatively stable in the Seine Bassin at around 20 million Tonnes per year, however, volumes in the Bassin Nord Est however have lost almost the half from 10 million tonnes (2000) to 5,8 million tonnes 2012, reasoned by a drop in mineral fuels. The Seine Bassin is dominated by Crude materials incl. building materials, much reasoned by the large port of Rouen being a multi-modal port, which specialises in bulk and agri-bulk commodities. The Bassin Nord-Est shows a considerable amount of agricultural products.

Stakeholders

Table 8 Stakeholders involved in the IWT process

		Main actors	Detailed actors	French Pilot
Transport function		Infrastructure manager		
			Rail	SNCF réseau
			Road	SANEF/SAPN ; région Grand Est
			IWT	VNF
		Transport companies		
			Shipping line	
			Trucks	Mauffrey/MGE/Transports Vignerons/Transports Foulon
			rail freight operators	SNCF + others
			barge operators	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei...
		Inland terminal		
			Terminal operator	Seine : Haropa, Moselle : The company managing the whole is the syndicat mixte pour la gestion des ports lorrains ; the public logistics operator is a concessionaire
		Deepsea ports		
			Terminal operator	
			Port authority	Seine : Haropa
			etc.	
		Logistics service providers		
		1 PL (producers delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei...	
		2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei...	
		3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei...	

			4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transtest, Specherei...
			5PL (= 4PL + view on network rather than chain)	
		Shipper / cargo owner		
			Sender	depends on the needs (in waiting of the questionnaire)
			receiver	depends on the needs (in waiting of the questionnaire)
Regulation		Regulators of IWT		
			EU	Yes
			Federal government	Ministères chargés de l'économie, du budget, des transports, de l'agriculture, du tourisme, de l'énergie, de l'environnement, de la Transition écologique et de la Cohésion des territoires ; agence de l'environnement et de la maîtrise de l'énergie (organisme de financement public) ;
			Local government	Communauté Urbaine Le Havre ; Seine métropole ; métropole du Grand Nancy ; CCNR ; CIM (Commission Internationale de la Moselle) ; some EPCI
Public interest		People		
			Citizens living near the waterway	
			environmental group(s)	France nature environnement, or more depending on the needs
			Local interest groups	
			etc.	
L i				

		Sector organisations representing private companies	Farmers	
			Power plants	Syndicat des énergies renouvelables
			Tourism sector	
			Transport sector	Entreprises fluviales de France
				Union des Chargeurs de Lorraine
				Organisation des PME du transport routier
				Association des utilisateurs de transport de fret
				Union des transporteurs publics et ferroviaires
				Fédération nationale des transports routiers
			etc.	Union des Entreprises de Transport et de Logistique de France
Researchers		Universities		
			University1	
			University2	
		Knowledge institutes		
			Knowledge institute 1	
			Knowledge institute 2	

Commitments for green growth

To preserve the ecological advantage of the river, there are numerous initiatives and experiments in terms of greening: electric motorization, natural gas or even hydrogen.

Voies navigables de France, as the national waterway operator, is increasing its initiatives to support the sector in this challenge and enable it to strengthen its ecological performance.

It is therefore quite natural that VNF signed in July 2021 Commitments for Green Growth with the State, E2F (Entreprises Fluviales de France: France Inland waterways Companies) and economic operators in the sector. These aim to:

- reduce river GHG emissions by 20% within 10 years;
- promote the electrification of the quays with an overall objective of 150 electric terminals on the quay by 2024;

- experimenting with alternative low-emission motorization solutions and facilitating experiments in innovative motorization, in particular with the support of the Fleet Modernization and Innovation Assistance Plan (PAMI) implemented by VNF.

AUTF Partnership

VNF and the Association of Freight Transport Users (AUTF) signed a partnership agreement on September 13 of 2021, which aims to accelerate the conversion of shippers to clean logistics as part of the FRET 21 approach, and particularly to logistics river.

VNF/SNCF Network partnership

January 25, 2021 was marked by the signing of the national VNF-SNCF network agreement, which notably provides for joint actions to develop multimodal rail/river flows.

The collaboration between SNCF Réseau and VNF continued with a territorial application in the Normandy and Ile-de-France sectors in February 2021.

Partnership for river transport on the Seine with Haropa

Table 9 Stakeholders involved in the IWT process

	Main actors	Detailed actors	French Pilot
Transport function	Infrastructure manager	IWT	VNF
	Transport companies	barge operators	CFT, Coalis, SCAT, transports Lalemant, transports Blanchet, Cemex, Lafarge-Holcim, Marfret ; VNF is currently discussing with 5 other freight forwarders/shippers. They represent 70 to 80% of fret IWT in France.
	Tech provider	Supplier 1 of technology	UNEW, Euromobilita
		Supplier 2 of technology	CERTH
		WP3 partners developing management system	
Regulation	Regulators of IWT	EU	
		Federal government	VNF, Cellule ministérielle de veille opérationnelle et d'alerte
		Local government	
		CCNR (?)	

On the occasion of a webinar "River Logistics Axis Seine" for economic actors in November 2021, VNF and HAROPA PORT signed a partnership agreement for the development of river transport on the Seine. The competitiveness of the supply chain as well as the ecological and energy transition are at the heart of the objectives of this partnership.

Signature of the port charter

A commitment charter for players in French supply chains was signed in the presence of the Minister for the Sea and the Minister Delegate for Transport in October 2020. This charter is a major opportunity to promote intermodality and mass transport.

6.2.3. Pilot Actors & Involved Systems/Technologies/Infrastructure

Technology

CEDRE - a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading (France, Europe), developed in WP8

- The platform should be connected to the transport management system of large companies, allow individual shipowners to declare freight transport.
- It should issue digitalized transport documents, secured and editable by authorized parties
- It could give authorized customers (shippers or freight forwarders) access to information on empty barges

Table 10 CEDRE Business Model Canvas

BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS				
KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSITION	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
Chargers , Shippers boatmen Navigation managers (French, Belgian, etc.) Organization/ Professional Association ICC, Regions, Departments ADEME Ministry of Transport European Commission (DG MoVe, Nalades) Universities (Gustave Eiffel,	Sale of services Own management of an online site data monetization KEY RESOURCES Own and outsourced software Construction of a data acquisition platform based on a Keeex solution Information dissemination platform VNF database (VNF data owner) Human resources : sales force ?, marketing ?	reduction in transport costs due to optimized boat rotations, by reducing the number of boats traveling empty; security in commercial transactions (dematerialized & secure transport documents) improve the commercial relationship between customers and river service providers, reassure potential customers (move from artisanal type formalities to an industrialized chain) Internal VNF : reduction of costs linked to the process of collecting and checking data, securing revenue linked to tolls for goods, linked to the collection of data from principals (based on commercial data, therefore authentic)	Information meetings dematerialized transport documents statistical queries, KPI Internal VNF : billing data and statistical production CHANNELS professional federations of shippers freight forwarders river carriers, ports, VNF territorial development services Norlink, Medlink, Haropa VNF transport events e-mailing et LinkedIn Belgian or Dutch (or even German) counterparts or partners of VNF	river carriers (craftsmen, industrial companies), charterers, transport contractors (industry & distribution shippers), freight forwarders, port operators (private or public), waterway management bodies outside France, administrations (river police & gendarmerie), Internal VNF (accounting services, estate management, statistical production, territorial departments)
COST STRUCTURE IT (Build + Run), marketing cost, communication, training & support		REVENUE STREAMS Identification of empty boats allows customers to charter them at competitive prices, from carriers who can lower the cost of their trips (lower fuel consumption) and the CO2 emissions of their trips, pooling of the hold VNF : increase in tolls resulting from better capture of transport data (at source), and specific subscriptions depending on the players		
Designed for:		Designed by:		Version:

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Source Own elaboration

Use of sensors developed in WP8

A Data Hub for sensor data (logistics and maintenance: position of barges on the Seine, buoys data, etc.) could be set up, with webservice/API to connect with digital twin. It could be compatible with the various standards, in particular with regard to the barge geolocation market.

Navigation facilitation and safety

Request from shippers for river transport necessary for the logistics of rail infrastructure works in Greater Paris :

- Barges (not subject to the AIS obligation) must be geolocated

The service could be free for the manager and users who have a geolocation system, interfaceable with the information systems of managers and other stakeholders.

Recommendations for geolocation standards could be proposed.

- Users should know the availability of parking and handling areas : camera on the platform and AI detection to train should be tested

A demonstrator site should be created on the Louis Blériot wharf (Haropa manager) where unused barges present nuisances for local residents (issues of monitoring wharf occupancy, barge storage, adaptation of the police regulations of navigation). An artificial intelligence, trained in the “laboratory”, should be tested on the demonstrator site.

Flood management on the Moselle river

The buoys, which delimit the navigation channel, are impacted when the currents are really strong and most peculiarly by (during and after) floods.

After a flood, the manager of the waterways (VNF) must be able to identify as quickly as possible which ones have left their place of anchorage and are going down the river in order to put them back in place as quickly as possible, to allow for a safe navigation. If it takes more time, it has to identify them and give the information to the users of the waterways.

To do so, remote monitoring/remote management of the buoys and automation of information dissemination should be put in place.

Data is buoy position and status of the buoy light.

An experiment will be carried out on the cross-border reach of Apach : narrow channel with regularly degraded buoys (floods, jams, boats)

The dissemination of information to users by AvisBat will be standardized.

The prioritization of buoy equipment (160 buoys over 150 km of Moselle) will be studied for possible deployment.

A report will be produced in order to propose a format of smart buoys; the following issues could be addressed:

- Standardization of user information
- Choice of satellite network for positioning

Tools for infrastructure maintenance

Radar inspection (WP2) and acoustic monitoring (WP5) technologies will be tested in the laboratory. They could also be tested on locks, subject to compatibility with operating constraints. An evaluation of the relevance of the numerical models and their mode of entry could be carried out. VNF could use the results to feed into the maintenance, renovation and modernization program. Recommendations on the availability and free access to the technical documentation of the works could be made.

Radar Inspection (developed in WP2)

Transfer of technology from the rail industry to develop a sub-surface inspection system through non-destructive examination of waterway infrastructure should be tested. The inspection could be carried out on a lock wall. VNF could use this information to feed into the maintenance, renovation and modernization programme.

Acoustic monitoring (developed in WP5)

Acoustic monitoring of a lock could be tested. With the monitoring measurements, models could create a multidimensional cluster of points declaring the good operation. Statistic models could then provide a confidence of good operation. VNF could use this information to feed into the maintenance, renovation and modernization programme

Information system

VNF has an information system (planning and real time) which covers infrastructure (operation, maintenance and asset management), water management, and boats.

Infrastructure

VNF has a database of structures, for asset management, and computer-assisted maintenance management software. VNF has a single digital twin (in the sense of 3D visualization) used to test a centralized lock remote control station (this test and training platform can therefore be used to train operators of VNF structures in scenarios of crisis management).

Water

The aGHyre application, available on the VNF Internet, allows you to know, in almost real time, all the data that can be disseminated related to water (levels, flows, structure positions, water reserves) that measures or obtains Navigable Ways of France. All distributable data from the aGHyre application are freely accessible without authentication. They can be consulted in the form of tables and graphs through the list of sites, dashboards, or the GIS (Geographic Information System) of VNF.

In order to optimize its hydraulic management, particularly in the context of strong climate change, VNF renewed on January 12, 2023 its partnership with Météo France dedicated to the management of the river network. For VNF, it is a question of benefiting from detailed meteorological information, anticipated and adapted to its network in order to optimize its management in the face of the climatic challenges encountered (floods, low water levels).

In addition, a partnership with INRAE has been set up. VNF is taking part in two research projects in order to improve its knowledge of hydro-climatic projections in the medium term and on the horizon of climate change. The PREMHYCE project makes it possible to have flow forecasts for watercourses at low water level. The performance of the tool as a decision support tool is studied by VNF. VNF has also integrated the national EXPLORE 2 project. This project is the continuation of the EXPLORE 2070 project. It aims to produce new hydro-climatic projections for France by 2100 on the basis of the most recent results of the IPCC and with more robustness.

In addition, in order to strengthen cooperation between VNF and SCHAPI (Central Hydrometeorology and Flood Forecasting Support Service), a partnership agreement was signed on October 23, 2019. As part of this agreement, work adaptation of the databases was carried out to allow mutual provision of data in real time for better flood management.

An international working group has been set up through the EEIG Seine-Escaut, to deal specifically with water management on the scale of the 1,100 km of this wide-gauge navigable axis between the Seine basin and the ports of Dunkirk and Northern Europe. It brings together technical specialists from VNF, the Service Public de Wallonie and De Vlaamse Waterweg.

User information

The data for the information of users is made available on a European portal (<https://eurisportal.eu>) to the European RIS standard.

EuRIS presents all the waterways and traffic information of thirteen European countries on maps or in tables, with

- a real-time traffic image
- information on the position of the boats according to your rights
- notices to skippers
- water levels, flows, free heights under bridges, moorings in real time
- information on waterways, bridges, locks, berths, terminals...
- opening times of locks and movable bridges
- route and trip calculation
- the duration of the journeys and the estimated time of arrival at destination
- ...

EuRIS provides easy access to all useful information for users (marine, shipowner or logistics operator) on the main European waterways. You can register your boats there and follow their route, receive a message when one of the boats passes a certain point on the network and request information on other boats, trips and loads. The owner of the information manages the permissions to access it.

The RIS Directive provides a Europe-wide framework for the implementation of the following information services: Notices to Skippers (NtS standard), AIS infrastructure (Tracking and Tracing), Electronic Ship Reporting, Electronic chart display and information system for inland navigation (inland ECDIS).

Every Friday, major navigation stops and restrictions in progress on the network are made available on the VNF website. Notices to skippers on events, planned or unforeseen, which may occur and modify navigation conditions, are also available there.

Navigation can be prepared on the VNF website with the provision of ECDIS charts, navigation timetables and a river route calculation, the list of stoppages, the map of anchorages and the police regulations of the navigation. There is also access to the SIF Seine and the NAVI mobile application, which offers a real-time river route calculation service.

VNF does not have a specific information system for its programming of stoppages on the waterway.

Ports

Port information systems are not harmonized and are not compatible with the information systems of waterway managers

Ports are not very open to data sharing, for commercial reasons, in particular on the contents of containers; however, there are exchanges with the port of Dunkirk

Railway

SNCF Réseau has an information system for scheduling unemployment.

6.2.4. Pilot Execution Plan

CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading (France, Europe)

1. Obtain the agreement of river transport companies on the creation of gateways between their systems and VNF information system : first half 2023
2. The content of data and the flow of transport documents between freight actors will be described : 2023
3. A demonstrator web service, with at least one of the companies having given their agreement, will be created : 2023
4. Transform VNF system to open it up to principals or charterers : 2023
5. Define Specifications to create an online service for producing & updating transport documents (bills of lading or waybills) : 2023
6. Creation of an online service for producing and updating transport documents (bills of lading or consignment notes) : 2024
7. The advisability and feasibility of creating a system for sharing hold data available to authorized persons (charterers especially) could be studied : 2025

Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety

1. A demonstration site should be built on Seine : 2023
2. A report could be produced on the use of artificial intelligence to know and transmit information on the occupation of quays by a boat or a barge: 2024

Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle river

1. An experiment should be carried out on the cross-border reach of Apach : 2023
2. A report could be produced in order to propose a format of smart buoys: 2024

Tools for infrastructure maintenance

VNF could test, as core activities, two technologies (developed on WP2 and WP5) on locks to collect data, aimed at improving infrastructure maintenance : radar inspection and acoustic monitoring

Both technologies will first have to be validated in a laboratory.

Then they could be tested on site, subject to the compatibility of their implementation with the operating conditions.

VNF could use this information to feed into the maintenance, renovation and modernization programme.

1/ The first technology to collect data is **radar inspection**

It is a transfer of technology from the rail industry to develop a sub-surface inspection system through non-destructive examination of waterway infrastructure.

The technology could be tested for the inspection of the vertical walls of lock chambers.

- EUMO is focusing on:
 - Implementing a new technology concept based on pivoting and rotating step-by-step the GPR for multiple scanning of wall areas, which is different to the rotating GPR that was used for rail tunnel scanning, and believed to be more efficient for this case;
 - Integration of the GPR equipment onto a system capable to perform the scanning of lock side-walls.
- UNEW is focusing on:
 - Testing the new concept in the lab and in relevant environment (a concrete wall similar to the lock's walls), being supported by EUMO in this activity

Relevant visualisations are expected in April 2023.
 - Developing method and algorithms for data processing and visualisation.
- Site visit in November 2022
- Laboratory tests in early 2023
- Lock inspection in 2023

NOTE! The timetable given is indicative and takes into account the initial planning carried out at the beginning of project development. In the process of further work, the given timelines will be reviewed and updated (updated data will be provided in D6.2).

A test on the large-gauge lock at Blénod-lès-Pont-à-Mousson could be planned for the end of the first half of 2023, subject to the compatibility of their implementation with the operating conditions.

Another test on the large-gauge lock could be planned in 2024, subject to the compatibility of their implementation with the operating conditions.

- Evaluation report on the relevance of digital models and their input mode : 2024

The scanning output will inform 2 relevant issues:

1. “Probable” indication on where to look further and what to expect behind an arbitrary portion of the wall scanned (specific problematic areas)
2. Potential abnormalities in the wall structure.

EUMO will operate the scanning system and provide the raw data, and UNEW will process the data to produce visualisations (defect, for example cracks, voids or rebar corrosion ...). After that, they will support VNF in understanding the processed data and determining the nature of abnormalities and severity of defect in lock walls.

Assessment and grading of defect severity, to inform maintenance actions, is a follow up step requiring data processing.

All three could work on how to use the data for improving VNF maintenance plan and overall renovation and modernization programme.

2/ The second technology to collect data is **acoustic emission**

The technology could be tested for monitoring lock gates and their motorized equipment.

The CERTH university will develop and test in laboratory equipments and systems.

- Laboratory tests in early 2023
- Lock equipment by CERTH before June 2023

The technology could be first tested on field, on April 2023, on Italian pilot waterlocks. AE strategy will be re-evaluated after these tests, before proceeding with other pilots measurements

A test on large-gauge locks on Seine (Méricourt, Poses-Amfreville) is considered for the end of the first half of 2023, subject to the compatibility of their implementation with the operating conditions.

A test on large-gauge locks on Moselle (where the radar inspection system is supposed to be used) or on Great Saone (north of Lyon town) could also be considered, subject to the compatibility of their implementation with the operating conditions.

The measurements will take place 1-2 days for each site.

- Evaluation report on the relevance of digital models and their input mode : 2024

The CERTH university will use models to create a multidimensional cluster of points declaring the good operation of the lock gate.

Using statistic models university will then provide a confidence of good operation.

6.2.5. Expected Pilot Results & Assessment Plan

This section outlines the key performance indicators that will be scrutinized to gauge the effectiveness and success of the testing phase. By meticulously detailing the assessment framework, this chapter lays the foundation for an informed evaluation of the pilot's impact:

Table 11 French pilot KPIs

Proposed KPIs	This KPI will be measured by- test or simulation	Measuring data
E1-Capacity levels during extreme weather events	test	- Develop the wide-gauge network, particularly within the framework of the Seine-Escaut network: compliance with the program validated and financed by Europe - Reliability of structures: number of breakdowns/structures/year
E2-Early warning systems for extreme weather (extreme weather incidents detected / month)	test	Progress rate of the modernization of the Hydraulic Management of the network
E3-Capacity levels during disruptions	test	- Availability rate (in %) on the wide gauge - Identify and assess the impacts of climate change on the network
E4-Real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring (% of network covered)	test	Functional state indicator of the structures
E5-Tracked vs total shipments (% /month)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
E8-Actual vs planned shipments (% of on-time shipments)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
E11-Resource availability / Asset management (% of assets digitalised/connected)	test	Integrated river-rail scheme for combined transport including the operating mode for "transfer" of flow between river and rail in the event of a service continuity problem (flood, damage, structure, line interruption): drawing up of a map on the Ile-de-France basin

E12-Operational cost of a fixed route (E12-euro/cargo unit/km)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)	test	Provision of RIS data on each basin of the wide-gauge network in the European EURIS portal
ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT	test	Additional tonne-kilometres (Tk) generated by the Modal Shift Assistance Plan
ENV2-Recycled materials	test	% of non-hazardous sediment recovered
ENV3-Evaluation of material composition applied by IWT infrastructure	test	- Progress rate of the works compliance program to strengthen ecological continuity - Number of works contracts including a provision in favor of sobriety énergétique
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)	test	Reduction rate of atmospheric pollutant emissions on engines supported by VNF: Nox
ENV5-PM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	test	Rate of reduction of atmospheric pollutant emissions on engines supported by VNF: PM
ENV6-GHG as CO ₂ e (tonnes of CO ₂ e / tkm)	test	Reduction rate of atmospheric pollutant emissions on engines supported by VNF: CO ₂
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (toe /tkm)	test	- Develop the wide-gauge network, particularly within the framework of the Seine-Escaut network: compliance with the program validated and financed by Europe - Reliability of structures: number of breakdowns/structures/year
S1-Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines	test	Progress rate of the modernization of the Hydraulic Management of the network
S4-Availability of multimodal transport information (Information publicly available - Likert scale)	test	- Availability rate (in %) on the wide gauge - Identify and assess the impacts of climate change on the network
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	test	Functional state indicator of the structures

6.3. Polish pilot

6.3.1. River Pilot Goals

Containerized maiden barge voyage conducted on Vistula river in 2021 within EMMA Extension (Interreg South Baltic) project shown, that local companies in the range of river pilot are interested in inland

waterway transport as a solution for their supply chains. Project parties involved in the voyage received substantial market feedback with the needs of cargo owners to develop and give the efforts towards rebuilding the supply chains with use of IWT based on existing infrastructure.

Thus, the main goal of the pilots is **to establish and test in market conditions new supply chain models with implemented IWT solutions**. The models will indicate and verify the factors which allow to choose cargo and supply chains most suitable for IWT implementation in current navigation conditions on selected routes incl:

- a) Terms of delivery
- b) Cargo volume
- c) Flow frequency
- d) Type of cargo
- e) Time flexibility

Four pilots with different types of cargo chosen on market indications as above will verify the usability of IWT in current infrastructure availability and **outline the most required investments in the pilot areas**. At the same time the voyage parameters will be compared with the other transport modes which are currently in use (road or rail) in terms of capacity, transit time and market availability.

Secondary goal of the pilot is to **develop and implement the technology of intelligent (smart) buoys** to provide real-time navigation parameters on selected waterways to improve the visibility of supply chains with tracing devices which are allowing to monitor the traffic on the waterways.

6.3.2. Pilot Case Specification

Pilot case will be performed by subcontracting specialized company (freight forwarder) chosen in tender process. Freight forwarder will be responsible for full supply chain preparation and performance, from loading to delivery point. Full pilot will contain four voyages in two different locations. Each of voyage should have dedicated scenario, accepted by the University of Gdansk prior to the execution.

Location

Three voyages will be performed on Lower Vistula river, between the Port of Gdansk, and a river quay selected and secured by chosen freight forwarder. First indication showed the ability to use shipper owned quay in Wloclawek or public quay in Chelmno managed by Wody Polskie (IWW infrastructure manager) depending on final type and quantity of cargo. Lower Vistula river will also become a location for smart buoy technology tests and its' implementation into supply chain.

Figure 26 Vistula river – north part
Source Own elaboration

Fourth voyage will be planned on the international IWW route via Odra (Oder) river from the Port of Duisburg (or, alternatively, Antwerp) towards Lower Silesia region, southern of Poland. Such long voyage allows to compare supply chain based on IWT with pure road transport and rail-road intermodal solution on similar routes.

Type of cargo

Pilot assumes to perform four voyages with different types of cargo to widely verify the suitability of developed supply chain models. Pre-project research indicated most common goods transported between seaport in Gdansk and pilot area (Kujawsko-Pomorskie Voivodeship):

1. Containers,
2. Fertilizers – unitized in big bags,
3. Grain – in bulk.

Fourth voyage performed on Odra (Oder) river will be performed with the containerized cargo. As a part of Intra-European supply chains freight forwarder should use 45'PW (pallet-wide) containers which are most suitable intermodal units, alternative for semitrailers used on European road transport.

Equipment

Freight forwarder's responsibility will include selection of carriers and handling partners with appropriate equipment to perform the pilots. Initial and final transport legs will be performed by road transport with the trucks. Main leg will be arranged with a tug and barges suitable for containerized or unitized general cargo and hopper barges for bulk goods.

Figure 27 IWW barge with containers on Vistula river
 Source Own elaboration

Cargo handling process at seaport terminals will be performed using terminal owned equipment – gantry cranes and reachstackers. Operations arranged on river quay, due to insufficient infrastructure, will require to use additional mobile handling equipment loaders and cranes arranged by chosen freight forwarder.

Figure 28 Containers handling on river quay and port terminal
 Source Own elaboration

Smart buoy technology developed by L-PIT will include water level devices which will provide details on:

- Navigation conditions: water level, bridge clearance, traffic and barge speed on particular voyage section
- Weather conditions: windspeed, temperature

6.3.3. Pilot Actors & Involved Systems/Technologies/Infrastructure

Actors

Infrastructural

- **PGW Wody Polskie**

IW infrastructure manager, provides the infrastructure for main leg of transport chains, share the knowledge and cooperates with technology provider on buoys location and its' features. Wody Polskie also manage and administrates the sluices and other hydrotechnical facilities to provide proper navigability class on pilot site. Furthermore, provides information on navigation conditions on IWW. Infrastructure manager is also responsible for collecting the toll for using infrastructure from IWW operator.

- **Sea terminal Operators (Port Gdansk Eksploatacja, Duisburg or Antwerp terminal) or reloading facility manager**

Arrange the handling procedures at loading/delivery terminals (locations) based on orders received from freight forwarder.

- **Authorities**

Gdansk Port Authority (GPA) – territory and aquatory manager at port area. In subject pilot, GPA controls barges traffic at port area, provides the approval for barge approach to indicated port terminals.

- **Logistics providers**

Freight forwarding company – creates the supply chain and execute the pilots based on chosen subcontractors mentioned in subject chapter and created logistics models. Indicates the Loading/delivery terminals and arrange handling and storage solutions in case of insufficient infrastructure availability. Freight forwarder will be also responsible for arranging first/last mile deliveries between terminals and pickup/delivery locations.

IW operator – executes the main leg transport by the order from freight forwarder. Schedules the voyages and notifies infrastructure manager and port authorities on expected schedule and routing.

Trucking companies – provides first/last mile – road delivery service by the order received from freight forwarder. Depending on chosen business model (and terminals) may be involved in delivery notification at terminals and may cooperate with them directly based on IT solutions developed by terminals.

Customs Broker (agent) – ensure proper documentation and cargo declaration for customs authorities (in case of import/export cargo)

- **Technology**

L-PIT – provides the intelligent buoy (sensors) technology according to experience and tips received from infrastructure manager and freight forwarding company. Intelligent buoy will be installed by L-PIT according to permits and instructions from infrastructure manager.

Technology

Smart buoys (or sensors) located on the voyage path will provide the information on sailing conditions across the river. Temperature, wind, water speed, depth and bridge clearance (if any). Sensors will send the received data to common cloud (?) and be shared to proper stakeholders (infrastructure manager -> IW operator -> freight forwarder)

Such data allows to make a decision by a IW operator (and freight forwarder) to run the barge voyage or use alternative mode of transport (rail or truck) to guarantee proper cargo flow in supply chains despite the obstacles caused by extreme weather conditions or disruptions on barge routing. Furthermore, sensors multiplication will allow to calculate the transit time and estimate barge arrivals for better transparency of supply chain, and scheduling terminal operations. Measured transit time will additionally give the input to compare current solutions in supply chains based on road/rail (as is) vs supply chain built on IW solution.

Implemented technology will improve the data availability on sailing conditions required by barge operators. Currently, subject data is available on infrastructure manager website (not regularly updated) or via phone. Providing the accurate date on time will rush the decision making process which is arranged by freight forwarder in his supply chain control tower.

The correlation between the systems/ technologies, infrastructure along the process.

Data provided by the infrastructure can be easily shifted to proper stakeholders based on on-board units, or mobile applications to ensure wide availability of data to whole interested parties.

6.3.4. Pilot Execution Plan

Figure 29 Gantt chart – polish pilot
Source Own elaboration

6.3.5. Expected Pilot Results & Assessment Plan

Executed pilot voyages will provide comprehensive view of the existing supply chains configuration and will verify the usability of IWT in modern logistics focused on flexibility and transparency. To measure the results and compare newbuilt supply chains with currently used solutions a set of KPI's has been developed. Those KPIs will be scrutinized to gauge the effectiveness and success of the testing phase. By meticulously detailing the assessment framework, this chapter lays the foundation for an informed evaluation of the pilot's impact:

Table 12 Polish pilot KPIs

Proposed KPIs	My understanding of this KPI/my definition (optional)	This KPI will be measured by- test or simulation	What technology is this KPI related to	Measuring data
E5-Tracked vs total shipments (% /month)	% of shipments in measured supply chain chosen for pilot covered by GPS	test	GPS on barge board / trucks	Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution

	real time tracking devices			
E6-Operational efficiency (tonnes/km)	Total Tonne-km or TEUkm for containerised cargo transported during the pilot	test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
E7-Status updates (updates/hour)	A number of shipment status (ETA update) sent to forwarder/customer during the pilot	test	intelligent buoys	Arrival time (ETA for the shipments)
E8-Actual vs planned shipments (% of on-time shipments)		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
E9-Delays/Waiting times (E9- actual-estimated time of arrival as absolute value per shipment)	% of shipments on time - verification - delivery notification time vs real delivery	test	intelligent buoys	ETA Time based on intelligent buoys vs ATA provided by freight forwarder
E12-Operational cost of a fixed route (E12-euro/cargo unit/km)	providing final financial report on the total cost of supply chain / per tonne / per TEU	test		Cost assessment provided by freight forwarder - pilot performer
E13-Overall corridor transit time (minutes/km)	Measuring TT between cargo loading and cargo delivery	test	smart buoys	ETA Time based on intelligent buoys vs ATA provided by freight forwarder
ENV1-Share of freight transport on IWT	Measuring cargo freighted by ITW (multimodal) in total freight (per supply chain)	test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
ENV4-NOX (g/kWh or %m/m)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
ENV5-PM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
ENV6-GHG as CO₂e (tonnes of CO₂e / tkm)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report
ENV7-Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (toe /tkm)	Measuring real emission during the voyage	test		IWW Operator/freight forwarder report

S2-Accidents along the transport network				Only historical data, not directly referred to the pilots
S3-Time to react (response time/return time)				Based on Wody Polskie declaration
S4-Availability of multimodal transport information (Information publicly available - Likert scale)				As element of social survey, not directly referred to the pilot
S5-Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)				As element of social survey, not directly referred to the pilot
UG-1 Tons Freight / TEU Freight		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
UG-2 Barge cargo capacity utilisation		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
UG-3 IWW share in total supply chain distance [km]		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution
UG4 - Total manhours of people involed in supply chain		test		Freight forwarder responsible for pilot execution will provide report incl. pilot KPI's not possible to be measured by the technology during pilot execution

7. Innovation plan

CRISTAL exceptional ground-breaking innovations focus on adaptable, transferable and sustainable solutions. The transferability, adaptability and sustainability of the CRISTAL solutions will be proved as part of the project by customizing and adapting them to the specific setting and needs of the IWW and IWT of the river partners, that will act as living labs. Once implemented, evaluated and validated in the three pilots, the proposed adaptable innovations can be transferred to other IWT within Europe and beyond. The CRISTAL innovations are summarized in the table below where it is also clarified the piloting site where they will be tested and implemented and CRISTAL' WP leading the development.

Table 13 Ambition and proposed Innovation

Ambition and proposed Innovation	Piloting site	Involved WPs
Continuous measurement of water levels in free-flowing waterways: <i>Fibre Optic Sensors</i>	Po River (IT)	WP2, WP7
Continuous measurement of water levels in controlled waterways: <i>Intelligent Buoy System</i>	Vistula r. (PL) Moselle (FR)	WP2, WP8, WP9
Continuous information updating on waterways conditions and bridge clearance for vessels: <i>IWW Intelligent Communication Hub</i>	Vistula r. (PL) Moselle (FR)	WP2, WP9
Transforming IWW into intermodal chains: <i>Innovative business models</i>	Vistula r. (PL, Gdansk - Wloclawek) Oder r. (PL, Lower Silesia) - Mittellandkanal - Port of Antwerp)	WP2, WP9
Structural health monitoring of existing infrastructures for informing preventive maintenance: multi IoT Sensors and vessel mounted radar	Moselle (FR), Po River (IT),	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP7, WP8
Inform decision making processes towards a disaster resilient management: Decision Support System DSS webGIS platform	Po River (IT), Seine (FR)	WP3, WP7, WP8
A Corridor Visibility and Open data platform integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system	All sites	WP3, WP7, WP8, WP9
Synchromodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system: A toolbox of services for multimodal planning	All sites	WP3, WP7, WP8, WP9
Innovative Governance Model	All sites	WP4, WP7, WP8, WP9

The following table provides a description of innovative technologies and solutions to support the achievement of the goals of the CRISTAL project, which will be developed in each regional pilot:

Table 14 Ambition and proposed Innovation

Ambition and proposed Innovation	Italian pilot
Continuous measurement of water levels in free flowing waterways	Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS) develop by ENEA
Inform decision making processes towards a disaster resilient management: Decision Support System DSS webGIS platform	INPUT from “new smart daily report” developed by AIPo INPUT from “cold ironing (feasibility study)” developed by IV
A Corridor Visibility and Open data platform integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system	INPUT from “new hydraulic/statistic model” developed by AIPo INPUT from “new smart daily report” developed by AIPo
Synchromodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system: A toolbox of services for multimodal planning	INPUT from “new hydraulic/statistic model” developed by AIPo INPUT from “new smart daily report” developed by AIPo
Innovative Governance Model	“Guidelines for the sustainability and resilience of IWT&L” develop by SOGESCA Living Lab approach led by SOGESCA
Ambition and proposed Innovation	French pilot
Continuous measurement of water levels in controlled waterways: Intelligent Buoy System	Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle river by VNF
Continuous information updating on waterways conditions and bridge clearance for vessels: IWW Intelligent Communication Hub	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF
Structural health monitoring of existing infrastructures for informing preventive maintenance: multi IoT Sensors and vessel mounted radar	Radar inspection by UNEW and EUROMOBILITA
Inform decision making processes towards a disaster resilient management: Decision Support System DSS webGIS platform	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF

	CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF
A Corridor Visibility and Open data platform integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF
Synchromodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system: A toolbox of services for multimodal planning	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF
Innovative Governance Model	CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF
Ambition and proposed Innovation	Polish pilot
Shifting 20% of cargo in selected supply chains into IWW	Supply chain models, freight forwarder performing the pilots
Real time measurement of water levels, speed, bridge clearance	L-PIT intelligent buoy
Barge speed and ETA calculation	L-PIT intelligent buoy
Decision making process for logistics companies involved in supply chains – risk avoidance during extreme navigation conditions	L-PIT, Wody Polskie, IWW operator, freight forwarder

8. Expected impact of adopted innovations at the regional and EU level

The following descriptions are the result of the work and assumptions that took place at the CRISTAL proposal stage, and which are now being implemented operationally within the individual WPs.

The high-level impact of CRISTAL is for shippers and vessel operators to experience increased reliability and resilience of IWT infrastructure. With its focus on smaller waterways, which are often less advanced in their technology and with smaller budgets for infrastructure improvements, CRISTAL aims for affordable innovations which improve resilience and open-access digitalization tools which can be adjusted to other inland waterways,

beyond the three pilots of the project. Research indicates how important the improvement of the RIS system is for better efficiency of container transport. Such case studies have been done for the Oder and Danube. The development of an effective Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) across the tested transport networks will significantly enhance the corridor resilience through the reduction in the overall corridor transit time, the increase in the shipment visibility, the improved routing efficiency and the gradual shift to the intermodal transportation that is expected. The result will be a greener and digitalized supply chain transport corridor which will act as a gateway for the future developments in transport management systems. In recent EU CEF Transport project (FENIX), the tested pilots have recorded that similar transport management systems have already exceeded expectations with initial expected impact measurements showing: 5% increase on the modal shift, 10% increase on the routing efficiency, 20% on the shipment visibility, 20% reduction on the corridor transit time, 10% decrease on the number of accidents along the transport network and 30% reduction on the waiting times from the improvements on the reliability travel time. As a consequence of the increased resilience, the attractiveness of IWT for shippers increases, while it enables vessel operators to raise their productivity, hence be more competitive in relation to other modes of transport, in particular road transport.

Research has shown that the effects of transport infrastructures on the development of territories are not automatic⁵. The expected effects of the infrastructure are conditional, but the conditions of their appearance remain little explained⁶. Infrastructure improvement contributes to the shortening of geographical distance, which is always a constraint for the coordination of agents, but there are others important conditions that are at least as important, such as cultural or organizational constraints. In fact, a study on IWT in India has revealed that governance issues, policy bias, high cost requirements, and lack of river-interlinking are the most critical inhibitors for IWT development. This is why the development of innovative governance structures and of the corridor management system take such central parts within CRISTAL. They are essential to the realization of the target of an increase by further 20% of IWT. No measures have yet been developed to calculate the level (intensity) of cargo shift from road to inland waterway transport. Research rather focuses on the competitiveness of both modes and the factors influencing the shift to IWT. Most often the focus is on the analysis of freight costs or infrastructure investments. Practical, applicable and accepted solutions are key though. In the CRISTAL project stakeholder engagement is therefore focal to maximize the impact of the CRISTAL solutions. Whilst solutions developed within CRISTAL are conceived as generic solutions, adaptable to other environments, they will be trialed, tested and validated with the three pilot sites. This piloting ensures a verification of their impact. The results of the piloting will be evaluated and validated and will complete the guide maps for further exploitation of the adaptable solutions.

5 Offner, J.-M. (1993). Les « effets structurants » du transport : mythe politique, mystification scientifique. *L'espace géographique*, 22(3).

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6 Ollivro, J. (1997). *TGV et fonctions supérieures dans les régions Bretagne et Pays de la Loire*. Rapport établi à l'initiative du ministère de l'Équipement, du Logement, des Transports et du Tourisme, Université de Rennes II.

Table 15 CRISTAL expected impact

CRISTAL expected impact	Measurability and verification	Probability of realization
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measured and verified within pilots during event or by simulation • Measured and verified within digital twin by means of scenarios 	<p>High realization probability due to expertise of consortium and river pilots</p> <p>Furthermore, link to innovative vessel technology, including financing models, is part of CRISTAL;</p>
Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measured and verified within pilots during event or by simulation • Measured and verified within digital twin by means of scenarios • Piloting of corridor management system 	High realization probability due to modelling support, multimodal expertise within consortium
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measured and verified by means of use of transport volume on pilots by end of project • Modelled reduction of NOX/SOX, particulates, GHG as CO₂e. and particulates as a result of modal shift from road and rail • Further measuring by feedback and uptake realized by exploitation • Measuring by engagement of further IWT infrastructure providers as well as by vessel operators via platforms 	High realization probability due to development of targeted marketing concept, innovative governance model and business model to ensure financing possibilities of innovations developed within CRISTAL
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measured and verified within pilots during event or by simulation • Measured and verified within digital twin by means of scenarios • Piloting of corridor management system 	High realization probability due to modelling support, multimodal and organizational expertise within consortium, and high advice of Advisory Board in the project throughout and importantly representing the views of the stakeholders as a target group.

<p>Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation of material composition applied by IWT infrastructure partners within CRISTAL 	<p>Feasible, yet demanding target, taking into account the green procurement and the circular economy criteria⁷:the demand for the content of recycled material is increasingly frequent in public procurement than in the BtoB</p>
<p>Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.</p>	<p>Within the construction and development of CRISTAL solutions previously, jointly with stakeholders identified KPIs will be measured and integrated into the validation. Measuring of soil/water pollution will not deliver meaningful results due to the broad spectrum of influencing factors</p>	<p>High to medium realization probability; contradictory solutions to demand for use of recycled materials can occur;</p>
<p>Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.</p>	<p>WP4 is dedicated to this impact; measuring will be feasible by evaluation of the application of the innovative governance solution within the project’s pilots</p>	<p>High to medium realization; this requires the change in culture in IWT structures; such a change takes time and might only be kicked-off during the project duration</p>

Source CRISTAL proposal

By ensuring that CRISTAL solutions are developed taking into account the relevant standards and directives towards resilient infrastructures, communities and cities, their applicability and sustainability is further validated, e.g; ISO 14090 and ISO/DIS 14091 CONCERNING the Adaptation to climate change; ISO 20400 Sustainable procurement — Guidance ; ISO/TC 323 Circular economy, ISO/WD 59004 : Circular economy — Framework and principles for implementation ; ISO 14001 Environmental quality management ; Life Cycle Analysis and Life Cycle Costs ; ISO 50001 Energy management system ; ISO 26000 Guidance on social responsibility.

In line with the key objectives of CRISTAL, the expected impact of the project is, that it contributes to a minimum of 20% modal shift toward IWT, that it ensures reliability in 80% of disruptions, that resilience is improved to 50% and that the sustainability of IWT is improved. The multi-stakeholder approach of CRISTAL enables it to reach these ambitious targets.

Impact target 20% of modal shift:

The path to evidence the required 20% modal shift to the IWW is here the case study method, since a general modal shift is a virtual goal or strategic approach. The Polish pilot case confirms the requested modal shift

⁷ COM(2020) 98 final A new Circular Economy Action Plan For a cleaner and more competitive Europe

potential: VAN Cargo, as a forwarding company and intermodal operator in one, is constantly servicing a large Polish fertilizers producer with the seat in Włocławek. The distance varies between 230 km (by road) to 270 km (by barge). Total cargo transportation, based on 2020 equals 45,000 tons, in 100% carried by road transport. From the official statistics it is known, the producer engages VAN Cargo in 30% of its export and the rest is carried by other forwarders. By the assumption of big bag form of cargo unitarization (typical in this industry), an expected modal shift implemented by VAN Cargo can achieve 24,27%, when 1 weekly IWW service would be introduced, with the av. cargo capacity of 700 tons. This equals to the lowest capacity that can be ensured in typical navigation conditions and by low water levels. Another, and international trade relation serviced by VAN Cargo covers the route linking Lower Silesia and the Port of Antwerp for bulk containers. An average weekly volume exported from this region to Antwerp directly serviced and trucked by VAN equals to 168 TEUs. Assuming an average small barge cargo capacity of 30 TEU and 2 barges implemented to the service, the expected modal shift on the trade relation serviced by VAN Cargo can reach 35,71%.

Since barges typically have a carbon footprint some 75% lower than road, and with the use of hydrotreated vegetable oil this can be reduced by a further 90%, we can expect a reduction of externalities about 75% for GHG as CO₂e.

Impact target 80% reliability:

During WP4 a series of workshops carried out in the form of virtual meetings with the river pilot partners in preparation to this proposal it was identified, that in particular early warning systems for extreme weather, tools for real-time infrastructure monitoring and maintenance as well as of water levels in combination with corridor management systems and innovative, cooperative and more agile governance systems are needed to improve IWT reliability. These will be developed within the CRISTAL project, answering the most pressing needs of the IWT providers.

To optimize the impact of CRISTAL, a detailed communication, dissemination and exploitation plan will be developed at the beginning of WP11. In the following, a first version of this plan is mapped out.

Topics and descriptions in the exploitation strategy will take into consideration the EC “Innovation Radar 3” (which aims at identifying and supporting high-potential exploitable results). Exploitable results and exploitation channels will be identified in the exploitation strategy, across four categories; 1) Commercialization, including business models and consultancy service portfolios based on the project tools; 2) Research, including follow-up research, citations by project-external researchers and use of project research findings in teaching and training, and informing further research; 3) Influencing policy and 4) Standardization.

Measures to maximize the impact

CRISTAL’s impact will be maximized through synergetic and measurable actions of Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation that will encompass:

- define an attractive and consistent visual identity (project templates, logotype, color scheme)
- targeting audiences with key messages
- plan dissemination outreach actions and dedicated means/channels for each stakeholder group ;
- making results available for use by others;
- making use of results in the project pilots and facilitating the use of results in further European waterways.

This will ensure that any valuable knowledge generated in the project is identified and not only made accessible to potential end-users but is also transferred to them.

Table 16 CRISTAL expected impact

CRISTAL expected impact	Actions planned in the Italian river pilot or related to some of the tasks
<p>Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidelines application to 10 companies and 5 public bodies • Gap analysis delivered for selected organizations • Provision of some input data to SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5

Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of some input data to the SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “New smart daily repor”t to allow better planning of transport operations by logistic operators: possible input to SCMS developed by WP3
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “New smart daily” report to allow better planning of transport operations by logistic operators possible input to SCMS developed by WP3
Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	N/A
Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines application to 10 companies and 5 public bodies Cold ironing possible implementation has the potential to reduce the environmental impact of the transport operations
Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Through the Living Lab governance framework application an agreed “long term collaboration” between the relevant national stakeholders could be reached.
CRISTAL expected impact	Actions planned in the French river pilot or related to some of the tasks
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of some input data to SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5 Radar inspection by UNEW and EUROMOBILITA Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle river by VNF
Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of some input data to the SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5 Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle river by VNF
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision of some input data to the SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5 Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle river by VNF
Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	N/A
Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.	N/A
Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF

Source CRISTAL proposal

9. Conclusions

In conclusion, the current situation of the inland waterway transportation (IWT) industry in each region, namely Poland, Italy, and France, reveals distinct challenges and opportunities unique to each country.

Poland possesses an extensive inland waterway network, yet it lags behind more developed countries in terms of navigability and infrastructure. The majority of Poland's waterways do not meet the required technical classifications for international navigation, and the potential for inland waterway transport remains largely underutilized. The focus on road, rail, and other modes of transport has led to neglect of the waterway infrastructure. While there are arguments in favor of developing waterways, such as connecting seaports and addressing environmental concerns, the lack of funding and maintenance has hindered progress.

In Italy, the Po River serves as a prominent inland waterway for freight and passenger transportation. The country's strategic geographical position has driven the emphasis on road and rail transportation networks, yet initiatives to shift freight traffic from road to rail are gaining traction. Italy's involvement in key European transport corridors contributes to its significance in the broader logistics landscape. The presence of intermodal terminals and initiatives to support inland waterway and rail transportation demonstrate the nation's commitment to sustainable transportation solutions.

France's transportation landscape is dominated by road transport, with roadways handling a substantial portion of the country's goods movement. Despite possessing a well-developed network of navigable rivers and canals, inland waterway transportation plays a minor role in France's overall freight transport. Rail freight faces challenges due to priority given to passenger trains and infrastructure bottlenecks. The government's initiatives, such as the rescue plan and climate targets, signal a commitment to reviving rail freight and promoting more sustainable transport modes.

In each region, the challenges and opportunities for inland waterway transportation are shaped by factors such as existing infrastructure, funding, regulatory frameworks, and broader transport strategies. While

road and rail remain dominant modes, efforts to optimize and develop inland waterway transportation align with the larger goals of sustainable and efficient freight movement within Europe.

The Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) planning and organization process reveals the intricate mechanics required to manage the movement of goods through inland waterways. This process involves strategic planning, coordination, and execution to optimize the utilization of rivers and canals for efficient and sustainable cargo delivery. The detailed process highlights the roles of various actors, from producers to IWW shipowners, in orchestrating the flow of cargo, with decision gates based on data from infrastructure managers guiding the transport route choices. The process's adaptability to digital infrastructure underscores the potential for streamlined interactions between logistics providers and transport authorities, enhancing overall efficiency.

The infrastructure management process involves a comprehensive range of activities to ensure the functionality, safety, and efficiency of river infrastructure. This includes tasks like setting maintenance goals, budgeting, routine inspections, preventive and corrective maintenance, and responding to emergencies. The process highlights the pivotal role of data analysis, documentation, and continuous improvement in optimizing maintenance strategies. The close relationship between infrastructure management and the logistics process is evident, especially in terms of data exchange and decision-making related to transport routes based on infrastructure availability. The approach of infrastructure management involves a blend of preventive and strategic methodologies, focusing on the maintenance of functional goals for infrastructure assets.

The chapter on the "Identification of main needs and problems affecting IWT" sheds light on the intricate landscape of inland waterway logistics. As the demand for sustainable transportation grows, the challenges and opportunities inherent in inland waterway transport (IWT) are unveiled. To harness its potential, stakeholders must address crucial issues such as infrastructure development, multimodal connectivity, network coverage, seasonal limitations, regulatory frameworks, environmental sustainability, funding, collaboration, awareness, and market competitiveness. By tackling these challenges, IWT can thrive, promoting balanced and environmentally friendly transportation systems. Furthermore, this study's insights into the specific challenges faced by regions like Italy, France, and Poland highlight the importance of cohesive strategies and innovative solutions for the successful development of their inland waterway systems.

Achieving resilience for river infrastructure entails multifaceted strategies to withstand disruptions, adapt to change, and maintain functionality. This involves comprehensive risk assessment, robust design and construction, consistent maintenance, safety measures, climate adaptation, collaboration, data utilization, and long-term planning. By addressing these areas, river infrastructure can bolster its resilience, ensuring continuous and efficient waterway systems for logistics. Recognizing the spectrum of disruptions that can affect Inland Waterway Transport (IWT), including natural, infrastructure, cargo, human-related, vessel-related, security, unforeseen events, congestion, and IT-related issues, stakeholders must employ contingency plans, flexible strategies, and consistent communication to manage and mitigate these challenges. The CRISTAL project, supplemented by the SCMS tool, stands to significantly enhance the industry's ability to navigate these complexities within the corridor.

The CRISTAL innovation plan is geared towards developing adaptable, transferable, and sustainable solutions that address various challenges in inland waterway transportation. These innovations will be rigorously tested and customized within the living labs of the IWW and IWT river partners, demonstrating

their applicability and effectiveness. Once successfully validated, the CRISTAL innovations hold the potential to be replicated and integrated into other European and global inland waterway transportation systems, fostering improved efficiency, safety, and resilience in the industry.

In summary, the CRISTAL project aims to drive significant impact by enhancing the resilience and reliability of inland waterway transport (IWT) infrastructure. The project's focus on smaller waterways and affordable innovations seeks to bring about improvements that will benefit the industry as a whole. By developing open-access digitalization tools and a Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS), CRISTAL aims to increase visibility, routing efficiency, and modal shift while reducing transit times, accidents, and waiting times. The project acknowledges the importance of innovative governance structures and the role they play in overcoming barriers to IWT development, aiming for a 20% increase in modal shift. To ensure maximum impact, CRISTAL employs a comprehensive communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy, with the goal of creating a resilient, sustainable, and efficient IWT system for the future.

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13. Appendices

To analyze the content of the annexes, enlarge the diagrams in this Word file

Annex0 IWT disruptions

Disruption/Risk	Place of appearance	Source of information	Effect	Solution	Probability of occurrence
Flood / surge	Shipping Route	IMGW/RZGW (Woody Polskie) / AIPo, National and Regional Civil Protection Agencies / VNF	Closure or restriction of shipping lane capacity	Reducing the speed of water flow, Choosing an alternative waterway, changing the mode of transport	medium
Maintenance work on the shipping lane	Shipping Route	Infrastructure Manager (Woody Polskie) / AIPo, Infrastructure operators / VNF	Closure or restriction of shipping lane capacity	Choice of alternative waterway, change of mode of transport	low
Water level too low	Shipping route	IMGW/RZGW (Woody Polskie) / AIPo, Infrastructure Venete / VNF	Closure or restriction of shipping lane capacity	Choice of alternative waterway, change of means of transport	medium
Damage to cargo during transportation	Shipping route, port area	Terminal operator, carrier	Refusal to accept cargo, disposal	Prior cargo insurance of cargo	low
Loss of cargo during carriage	Shipping route, port area	Water police, carrier, infrastructure manager	Closure or restriction of shipping lane capacity	Work on clearing the route, liquidation of damage	low
Lack of availability of the barge before the start of the transport (loss of seaworthiness)	Shipowner's office	Shipowner's office, Inland Navigation Authority	Non-availability of equipment	Search for an alternative vessel or shipowner or change of means of transport	medium
Protest by environmental organizations	Shipping route, port infrastructure	Track observation - telephone	Delay, change of shipping route	Provision of additional protection of objects / units	high
Inoperable infra. facilities (repair, breakdown) e.g. damage to the bottom of the canal	Point infrastructure	Infra-structure manager (RZGW website, telephone)	Delay, change of shipping route	Planning another route of transportation, change of means of transport	medium
Closure of infra. facilities due to fortuitous events e.g. partitioning by pontoon bridge, failure of lifting drawbridge, swing bridge, military maneuvers, seasonal events, sports events, etc...	Shipping route	Infrastructure manager (RZGW website)	Closure of shipping lane	Selection of an alternative waterway, change of means of transport	low
Congestion at terminals and port on/off	Selected terminals	Terminal operator, harbor master's office	Inability to carry out transshipments, delayed deliveries	Selection of an alternative terminal (if possible)	low
Breakdown/non-availability of personnel or handling equipment	Selected terminals	Terminal operator	Inability to carry out transshipments, delayed delivery	Selection of an alternative terminal (if possible)	low
Strike of port workers	Port terminals	Information in the terminal system, e-mail	Inability to carry out transshipments, delayed delivery	Selection of an alternative terminal (if possible)	low
Failure of a barge during a voyage	Shipping route, port area	Shipowner's office, Inland Navigation Authority/Shipping operators, AIPo, Infrastructure Venete, Port Authorities / VNF	Delay in delivery	Transshipment to an alternative vessel (if possible)	medium
Barge sinking	Shipping route, port area	Shipowner's office, Inland Navigation Authority/Shipping operators, AIPo, Infrastructure Venete, Port Authorities / VNF	Loss of cargo	Prior cargo insurance of cargo	low
Stranding of the barge	Shipping Route	Shipowner's office, Infrastructure manager	Closure or restriction of shipping route capacity, delayed delivery	Support of an additional pusher/hugger	averages
Adverse weather phenomena (big storms in part, storms, etc. - weather phenomena that limit visibility)	Shipping route, port area, first and last mile sections	IMGW/RZGW (Woody Polskie)	Suspension or slowdown of the transportation process / delayed delivery	Prior change of means of transportation, change of voyage schedule based on forecasts	medium
Unfavorable movement of material on the bottom of the shipping lane (restricting accessibility to infra.)	Shipping route, port area/handling places	IMGW/RZGW (Woody Polskie), Ship-owner	Suspension or slowdown of the transportation process / delayed delivery	Support of additional pusher/hug or dredger	medium
Unexpected random events (e.g., Pandemic covid19)	Shipping route, port area, sections of the first and last mile	all	Suspension or slowdown of the transport process / delayed delivery		low
Failures of vehicles making last mile deliveries	Sections of the first and last mile	Road carrier	Suspension or slowdown of the transportation process / delayed delivery	Securing additional vehicles (alternative carrier)	low
Vehicle delays due to traffic congestion, or delays of previously executed orders	Sections of the first and last mile	Road carrier	Suspension or slowdown of the transportation process / delayed delivery	Securing additional vehicles (alternative carrier)	medium
Technological incident (hazardous materials transport or logistic center/industry explosion ..., water pollution)	banks or shipping route	civil security	Closure or restriction of shipping lane capacity	Choice of alternative waterway, change of mode of transport	low
IT failure/cybersecurity	IT, automated and remote controlled hydraulic structures	IT department, remote control center operator	Non-availability of data and services, Suspension or slowdown of the transportation process / delayed delivery	Alternative information exchange, local and manual operation	medium
Lack of competent staff to operate or maintain infrastructure	IT, hydraulic structures, remote control centers	Infrastructure operator and maintainer	Closure or restriction of infrastructure and shipping lane capacity	skills transfer, knowledge management	medium

Annex1 "CRISTAL process.pdf"

Annex2 "CRISTAL IWW transport process.pdf"

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